

RESONATE

Resilient Forests for Society

Deliverable 5.6

Policy and practice recommendations for improving forest resilience

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

RESONATE adopted a comprehensive research approach to investigate how to enhance forest resilience in forests across Europe and their associated forest value chains. A focus of WP 5 was the synthesis of results derived from previous work packages and the development of guidance and recommendations for policy and practice. The deliverable builds on the scientific evidence developed in the RESONATE project as summarised in the scientific synthesis report (RESONATE Deliverable D5.5, Lindner et al. 2025). Most recommendations (Chapter 2) were first compiled as part of three policy briefs targeting i) Managing Forest Disturbances in a Changing Climate; ii) The Role of Biodiversity in Making Forests Resilient; iii) Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains (RESONATE Deliverable D6.7). The recommendations were discussed with stakeholders in a policy workshop in Brussels (10th February 2025), who ranked the importance of the RESONATE recommendations, suggested some additional recommendations and discussed potential trade-offs related to contrasting recommendations and identified further research needs.

In this synthesising report we present overall RESONATE recommendations for policy makers, practitioners and research. We discuss stakeholder feedback received on these recommendations and place the recommendations in the wider context of managing trade-offs and synergies on enhancing resilience in social-ecological forest systems.

KEYWORDS

Resilience assessment, forest management, disturbance risk management, climate change adaptation, biodiversity, forest value chain, social-ecological resilience, trade-offs.

1 Introduction

RESONATE aims to generate the required knowledge and practices for making European forests, the services they provide and related economic activities more resilient to future climate change and disturbances. RESONATE adopted complementary research approaches to investigate how to enhance forest resilience in forests across Europe and their associated forest value chains. A focus in WP 5 was the synthesis of results derived from previous work packages and the development of guidance and recommendations for policy and practice. In this report, recommendations for the main target groups – policy makers, practitioners and other stakeholders – are presented.

The deliverable builds on the scientific evidence developed in the RESONATE project as summarised in the scientific synthesis report (RESONATE Deliverable D5.5). Most recommendations (Chapter 2) were first compiled as part of three policy briefs targeting i) Managing Forest Disturbances in a Changing Climate; ii) The Role of Biodiversity in Making Forests Resilient; iii) Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains (RESONATE Deliverable D6.7). The recommendations were discussed with stakeholders in a policy workshop in Brussels (10th February 2025). The workshop was attended by 25 stakeholders (European and regional policy makers, forest owners and forest sector representatives, environmental NGOs), who ranked the importance of the RESONATE recommendations, suggested some additional recommendations and discussed potential trade-offs related to contrasting recommendations and identified further research needs. The results of the workshop are documented in a workshop report (Annex 1).

In this synthesising report we present overall RESONATE recommendations for policy makers, practitioners and research. We discuss stakeholder feedback received on these recommendations and place the recommendations in the wider context of managing trade-offs and synergies on enhancing resilience in social-ecological forest systems.

2 Recommendations for practice and policy

This chapter 2 highlights the policy recommendations based on rigorous multidisciplinary research within the RESONATE-project, including viewpoints from the varied group of researchers across Europe. We follow the policy brief division into three topics i) Managing Forest Disturbances in a Changing Climate; ii) The Role of Biodiversity in Making Forests Resilient; iii) Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains, as these three relate to important forest policy and resilience topics covered by RESONATE. The first group of recommendations addresses the management of climate change induced disturbances, the second targets biodiversity as a facilitator of resilience and relates to the old conflict of production vs. protection, whereas the third group emphasises markets and socioeconomics.

2.1 Managing Forest Disturbances in a Changing Climate

RESONATE Policy Brief #1 “*Managing Forest Disturbances in a Changing Climate*” presents three groups of recommendations on adapting forest management to increased disturbance risks, improving regulations and infrastructure to support climate change adaptation, and improved monitoring and planning. The recommendations comprise the following:

1. Adapt Forest Management to Disturbances

- 1.1. Consider short-term costs vs. long-term benefits: proactive management is more expensive upfront but reduces future damage.
- 1.2. Actively exploit disturbed patches as opportunities for climate change adaptation in forest management, using canopy openings to transition to mixed, climate-resilient tree species.
- 1.3. Incorporate post-disturbance forest structures into management (rather than eradicating them) to achieve important goals of sustainable forest management (e.g. increasing deadwood stocks in forests).
- 1.4. Adopt proactive approaches in both high-risk stands and those expected to become vulnerable in the future. These approaches may include establishing advance regeneration, reducing stand density and shortening rotation periods to lower risks.
- 1.5. Implement effective browsing control plans, which can be a decisive factor in post-disturbance restoration.
- 1.6. Develop best practices in adaptive management with recommendations for different forest conditions and disseminate to forest owners in local languages, e.g. via forest extension services.

2. Adapt regulations and infrastructure to support climate change adaptation

- 2.1. Support forest owners in realising adaptation measures with a combination of policy instruments, such as financial support, competence building and increased flexibility of regulations.
- 2.2. Remove the salvage requirement that is still a legal imperative in many EU countries and allow longer time windows for forest recovery following disturbances. This will facilitate the establishment of more diverse resilient forests.
- 2.3. Enable adaptation to climate change in guidelines for nature restoration and in habitat regulations for Natura2000 areas.
- 2.4. Safeguard nursery capacities and improve seed availability with the desired seeds for restoration, enabling potential use of reproductive material from neighbouring regions with suitable climate.
- 2.5. Support the establishment of storage and transport infrastructure to increase resilience in the wood value chain.

3. Improve Data and Planning

- 3.1. Forest restoration requires close monitoring and silvicultural interventions to ensure desired long-term development.
- 3.2. Mainstream newly available information on potential future disturbance risks into landscape level planning tools and process-based models to guide management decision making.
- 3.3. Use emerging remote sensing approaches to apply targeted disturbance management strategies.

The workshop participants assigned the highest priorities (Table 1) to the recommendations “Support forest owners in the realisation of adaptation measures” (2.1: 13 votes), “Consider short-term costs vs. long-term effects” (1.1: 8 votes) and “Adopt proactive approaches in high-risk stands” (1.4: 8 votes). Other recommendations such as “Implement effective browsing control” (1.5: 5 votes) and “Develop best practices in adaptive management” (1.6: 6 votes) were also considered important. These recommendations under 1. and 2. were especially highlighted by European policy makers as well as public and private forest owners. The forest-based industries and value chain actors put a special emphasis on the recommendation “Mainstream newly available information” (3.2: 4 votes).

Table 1: Policy Brief #1 recommendations on “*Managing Forest Disturbances in a Changing Climate*” prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups					Observers	Count sum
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups		
<i>1.</i>	<i>Adapt forest management to disturbances</i>	9	6	7	4	2	1	29
1.1	Consider short-term costs vs. long-term effects	3	2		2	1		8
1.2	Actively exploit disturbed patches	1		1				2
1.3	Incorporate post-disturbance forest structures							0
1.4	Adopt proactive approaches in high-risk stands	4	2	2				8
1.5	Implement effective browsing control		1	3	1			5
1.6	Develop best practices in adaptive management	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
<i>2.</i>	<i>Adapt regulations and infrastructure</i>	6	3	7	3	2	0	21
2.1	Support forest owners in adaptation measures	3	3	4	1	2		13
2.2	Remove the salvage requirement	2						2
2.3	Enable adaptation to climate change			2				2
2.5	Safeguard nursery capacities	1		1				2
2.5	Support the establishment of storage				2			2
<i>3.</i>	<i>Improve data and planning</i>	1	0	0	4	0	3	8
3.1	Forest restoration requires						1	1
3.2	Mainstream newly available information	1			4		1	6
3.3	Use emerging remote sensing						1	1
Sum		16	9	14	11	4	4	58

Note: Each participant could choose up to three recommendations that they considered as most important. The counts per group of recommendations (headings in italics) are sums calculated based on the votes per recommendation.

2.2 The Role of Biodiversity in Making Forests Resilient

RESONATE Policy Brief #2 “*The Role of Biodiversity in Making Forests Resilient*” specifies recommendations for policymakers at regional to EU level and for practitioners targeting forest owners and managers. The recommendations are as follows:

4. For policymakers (regional to EU level)

4.1. Promote tree diversity

- Support forests with tree species mixture with different functional traits to improve recovery from disturbances and make them more adaptable to climate change. Promote mixed forest with slow-growing broadleaved species and not only fast-growing conifers and support more mixture in coniferous stands.
- Foster the management of deer populations to reduce browsing impacts: Browsing can be a risk to tree diversity, because deer feed on specific species, e.g. oak.

4.2. Promote forest management for structural diversity

- Foster natural regeneration in an early state to support biodiversity.
- Advance uneven-aged forests to increase resilience and to speed up recovery from disturbances.
- Promote deadwood retention and other measures to increase the diversity of the forest structure, allowing multiple species to coexist by meeting their specific habitat requirements.

4.3. Provide financial and training support for forest managers

- Develop training programs for forest owners on how to manage forests in ways that benefit biodiversity and increase resilience.
- Offer subsidies or payments to forest owners who take steps to improve biodiversity, such as planting diverse species or maintaining deadwood.

5. For Forest Owners and Managers

5.1. Support ecosystem and economic resilience through diversity

- Diversify tree species to reduce the risk of large-scale losses during extreme weather events.
- Balance biodiversity and timber production by creating forests with a mix of tree types and structures that support different species.

5.2. Use disturbances to spark biodiversity growth

- Retain natural features: after storms or fires, leave some deadwood and fallen trees to support biodiversity and provide habitat for wildlife.
- Mimic disturbances (e.g. via prescribed burning) as a forest management method to increase forest resilience and biodiversity promotion

5.3. Diversify management measures

- Tailor your management to local needs: Use strategies that work for specific regions and conditions, ensuring both biodiversity and economic goals are met.
- Set small forest patches aside.
- Manage browsing efficiently.
- Foster natural regeneration in an early state to support biodiversity.

The workshop participants assigned the highest priorities (Table 2) to the recommendations “Support forests with tree species mixture” (4.1.1: 10 votes), “Develop training programmes” (4.3.1: 8 votes) and “Tailor your management to local needs” (5.3.1: 9 votes). In addition, other recommendations such as “Foster natural regeneration” (4.2.1: 4 votes), “Offer subsidies or payments” (4.3.2: 4 votes) and “Balance biodiversity and timber production” (5.1.2: 4 votes) were also considered important. There was a fairly common agreement of these priorities across the stakeholder groups.

Table 2: Policy Brief #2 recommendations on “*The Role of Biodiversity in Making Forests Resilient*” prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups					Observers	Count sum
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups		
Number of participants per target group		10	2	5	5	3	3	28
4.	For Policymakers	7	2	4	1	2	3	19
4.1	<i>Promote tree diversity</i>	3	2	3	0	1	1	10
4.1.1	Support forests with tree species mixture	3	1	1		1	1	7
4.1.2	Foster the management of deer population		1	2				3
4.2	<i>Promote forest management structural diversity</i>	4	0	1	1	1	2	9
4.2.1	Foster natural regeneration	2				1	1	4
4.2.2	Advance uneven-aged forests	1		1				2
4.2.3	Promote deadwood retention	1			1		1	3
4.3	<i>Provide financial and training support for forest m.</i>	3	2	2	0	4	1	12
4.3.1	Develop training programs	2	1	2		2	1	8
4.3.2	Offer subsidies or payments	1	1			2		4
5.	For Forest Owners and Managers	5	1	5	2	3	1	17
5.1	<i>Support ecosystem and economic resilience</i>	1	1	3	1	0	0	6
5.1.1	Diversify free species			2				2
5.1.2	Balance biodiversity and timber production	1	1	1	1			4
5.2	<i>Use disturbances to spark biodiversity</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
5.2.1	Retain natural features							0
5.2.2	Mimic disturbances				1			1
5.3	<i>Diversify your measures</i>	4	0	2	0	3	1	10
5.3.1	Tailor your management to local needs	3		2		3	1	9
5.3.2	Set small forest patches aside							0
5.3.3	Manage browsing efficiently							0
5.3.4	Foster natural regeneration	1						1
Sum		12	3	9	3	5	4	36

Note: Each participant could choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important. The counts per group of recommendations (headings in italics) are sums calculated based on the votes per recommendation.

2.3 Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

RESONATE Policy brief #3 “*Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains*” presents eight recommendations. They are not grouped as in the other policy briefs.

6. **Raise awareness of the risk gap** between forest managers and the wood processing industry. Streamlining adaptation efforts, promoting partnerships like cooperatives or producer groups, and encouraging information exchange across the value chain can help mitigate future supply shortage.

7. **Increase knowledge on forest adaptation in the wood processing industry** and develop efficient technologies to process more diverse types of wood provisioning e.g. species, assortments, qualities.
8. **Develop measures to safeguard the socio-economic resilience of forest management** by e.g. exploring risk-sharing agreements such as price guarantees or insurance schemes with forest owners and wood traders.
9. **Develop flexible, efficient harvesting technologies and logistics.** Rapid deployment of fully mechanised logging systems combined with flexible logistics solutions e.g. larger storage capacities, enhanced transportation networks and well-equipped wood terminals, can substantially moderate the surge of damaged wood to the market post-disturbance.
10. Wood processing industries should **acknowledge the growing risk of tipping points in softwood resource availability.** To support forest adaptation at scale, supply for valuable, long-life products should be prioritised and be complemented with secondary resources and cascade use.
11. **Explore alternative species and novel applications, including hardwoods.** Disturbances and risks are becoming more severe and will affect increasingly large regions. Given the enormous scale and long duration of the required technological transformation, the wood industry must start now to develop and invest into novel uses for alternative species. Along these lines we recommend:
 - 11.1. **Diversification and resource efficiency strategies:** i) broader portfolio of sawmill products, higher specialisation and niche products. ii) integrating downstream, “getting closer to forest”, e.g. larger mills acquiring sawmills or pellet plants. iii) supplier networks: with growing end-user demand for wood products, producers can benefit from more sophisticated partnerships and sizeable markets.
 - 11.2. **Innovation towards higher value-added products** exploring underused wood species, novel applications and growing markets in the construction sector and the bioeconomy.
 - 11.3. **Promote the cascading principle and a circular bioeconomy:** Increase valorisation of material by giving preference to high value applications first (e.g. wood construction, biorefinery) before low value mass use (e.g. bioenergy). Make use of the full spectrum of circular economy strategies (rethink, reuse, repair, repurpose, recycle, etc.) to enhance resource efficiency.
12. **Prioritise forest ecosystem services with high societal demand** and low demand resilience, such as soil protection or water regulation. Provide forest owners with financial incentives to ensure a sustainable supply of non-marketed forest ecosystem services.
13. **Invest in long-term, integrated resilience research.** We need to build up capacities to improve forest resilience in a wider sense. Forests, wood industries and society are interconnected, and the interplay of all drivers, actors, risks and potential solutions must be addressed from a systems point of view to enhance climate resilience of Europe’s entire forest value chains.

Table 3. Policy Brief #3 recommendations on “*Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains*” prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups					Count sum	
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups		Observers
Number of participants per target group		10	2	5	5	3	3	28
6.	Raise awareness of the risk gap	2		3	1			6
7.	Increase knowledge on forest adaptation		1		3			4
8.	Develop measures to safeguard socio-economic	1		2		1		4
9.	Develop flexible, efficient harvesting	1	1		2			4
10.	Acknowledge the growing risk of tipping points							0
11.*	Explore alternative species	2		2	1			5
11.1	Diversification and resource efficiency	2						2
11.2	Innovation towards higher value-added		1	1	1			3
11.3	Promote the cascading principle and a circular	4			1			5
12.	Prioritise forest ecosystem services	1						1
13.	Invest in long-term, integrated resilience	3		1	2	1		7

Note: Each participant could choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important.

* Some participants voted for the whole group, others voted for the sub-recommendation.

The workshop participants prioritised the value chain related policy recommendations as follows (Table 3). The recommendations group 11 “Explore alternative species” received the highest ranking (in total 15 votes; 5 participants highlighted the whole group, while 7 other participants highlighted the specific sub-recommendations). Secondly, the recommendations “Raise awareness of the risk gap” (6: 6 votes) and “Invest in long-term integrated resilience research” (13: 7 votes) received also significant attention. Furthermore, the recommendations (7 – 10: each 4 votes) were considered as relevant.

The highlighted priorities are quite spread across the stakeholder groups, showing a fair agreement among participants. A notable emphasis was given by the European Commission policy officers to the recommendation “Promote the cascading principle and a circular economy” (R11.3: 4 votes).

Figure 1: Three widely used definitions of forest resilience, with the broader definition of social-ecological resilience adopted in RESONATE embracing ecological and engineering resilience (Nikinmaa et al. 2020).

3 Recommendations per target group

In this chapter we group the most highly ranked recommendations (cf. Tables 1-3) and direct them to specific target groups in practice and policy. There are many levels and scales of action to enhance forest resilience, and a call to act on all fronts. The topic of forest resilience is a highly complex one (Figure 1), which was also reflected in the discussions with stakeholders in our policy workshop (cf. workshop report in Annex).

Yellow boxes: For each key recommendation we present reflections or statements by the policy workshop participants or RESONATE researchers that highlight needs to be considered in the implementation of the recommendations. *Individual statements/opinions are marked in “italics”.*

Across the three policy brief topics, different stakeholders ranked a broad range of recommendations as important (i.e. among the top three they could select). Only a few recommendations did not receive any vote for prioritisation. Overall, it can be concluded, that the selection of RESONATE recommendations was well supported by stakeholders.

It should be acknowledged that the number of votes cast differed between topics, because stakeholders did not vote on all topics (they could provide feedback on only two out of the three topics) and not everyone placed three votes per topic. Moreover, the number of separate recommendations voted on, varied across the three topics from 11 (value chain resilience) to 15 (biodiversity and resilience) and therefore there was an increased likelihood that in the latter topic a recommendation would not receive a top three prioritisation vote. For example, the recommendation related to browsing control was not prioritised under the biodiversity topic, although it was prioritised by stakeholders as an important adaptation measure for post disturbance management. Consequently, individual numbers in Tables 1 – 3 should not be over-interpreted, also considering the limited number of workshop participants.

3.1 Recommendations for forest owners and managers

The following key recommendations were seen as particularly important:

- **Tailor management choices to local needs.** Forest types, management practices and disturbance regimes differ. It is therefore crucial that forest owners and managers adopt strategies that work for specific regions and conditions, ensuring both biodiversity and economic goals as well as other ecosystem service demands are met.

“It is important for forest managers to adjust any proposed solutions to the local context. In this respect there is a need for numerous locally suitable measures.”

- **Proactive approaches** should be adopted in both high-risk stands and those expected to become vulnerable in the future. These approaches may include establishing advance regeneration, reducing stand density and shortening rotation periods to lower the risks. **Short-term costs vs. long-term benefits** should be considered when selecting proactive management measures. Proactive management can be more expensive upfront but likely to reduce future damage.
- **Diversifying tree species** is highly recommended for several reasons. It reduces the risk of large-scale losses from disturbances affecting single species (such as bark beetles in Norway spruce monocultures). Most importantly, the mixing of functionally different species will enhance resilience (e.g. since shallow and deep rooting species

access water from different soil layers to mitigate drought stress during extreme weather events). The **structural diversity** of forests should also be addressed. Mixing tree species and structures can also balance ecosystem service provisioning such as biodiversity and timber production. Moreover, diversity should also consider **soil organisms** as they have important roles in ecosystem functioning.

As a key measure, increasing biodiversity will help to create more resilient forests. Natural regeneration can play a significant role. However, it is not always the best choice as, in many forests, natural regeneration will favour spruce again if other seed sources are not widespread.

“Incorporation of functional diversity through appropriate tree species mixtures is a top priority for achieving higher resilience.”

When diversifying species mixture, it was shown to be beneficial to include a high share of slow growing species that are more resilient than fast growing ones.

- **Browsing control:** It is imperative to **implement effective browsing control plans** to facilitate and maintain enhanced species diversity in post-disturbance recovery. High game populations lead to selective browsing, often removing rare and desirable species from a climate change adaptation perspective (e.g. oaks).

Browsing is a major priority issue that prevents natural regeneration into more species-diverse forests. As a major factor across Europe, it is counteracting management efforts, acting as a big threat for climate adaptation and biodiversity. Lots of invested work and funding is being lost through browsing.

“A hot topic with many very conflictual views, new approaches are needed.”

“Apply a pragmatic approach on disturbed areas, take practical steps to start the transition to other tree species.”

- **Combine and plan different resilience measures at the landscape level.** Disturbance risk management, biodiversity restoration and forest connectivity should be integrated, rather than addressed in separate silo approaches. Increased diversity of forest types and management approaches distributes risks and at the same time offers opportunities to test the effectiveness of new adaptive management approaches.

3.2 Recommendations for forest landowner associations, forest-based industry and value chain logistics

- **Raising awareness about increasing climate impacts on forests and acknowledging the changing availability of forest resources.** This result was highly supported as regards to forest value chain practice. In regions affected by large-scale bark beetle outbreaks and droughts, softwood availability will decline in the longer run, whereas hardwood assortments remain abundant and underused. In the long-term, there will be a shift towards more broadleaved and mixed forests across Europe.

Encourage active forest management by means of creating a closer link between forestry and wood industry. Value chain is dependent on wood supply and needs to adapt in the long run to the changing species composition.

Joint advocacy of forest owners/managers and wood industry: “To reach a better agreement and cooperation, a common interest or incentive for both sides needs to be found. Besides these groups, the awareness of other stakeholder groups needs to improve. For example, in Austria and Germany, the national associations representing both groups hold regular meetings to define joint decisions and positions regarding upcoming trends and policies.”

- **Explore alternative species, new applications, hardwoods:** Due to the long duration of required technological transformation, the **wood industry should already start developing and investing in novel uses for alternative species** and should **increase valorisation of material** by giving preference to high value applications first (e.g. wood construction, biorefinery) before low value mass use (e.g. bioenergy).

How will industry deal with changing sourcing patterns related to more biodiversity-friendly forest management practices (including Continuous Cover Forestry, Close-to-Nature Forestry, more individual tree selection, etc)? The supply will become much more heterogeneous, stable access to certain types/assortments of timber is unlikely. Processing facilities need to become flexible to handle the variability of the future timber supply.

Hardwoods and softwoods are two completely different material groups: Different processing machinery adapted to hardwoods in sawmills is needed, i.e. bulky, very specialised, costly equipment with long-term investments. The produced products are also different and relate to very different, more specialised markets (less uniform commodities than softwoods). So, the practical realisation of this transition will be extremely challenging for sawmills and other wood industries.

Consumer and market perspective needs to be included: “While the forest is changing more and more to the provision of hardwoods, the market demand driven by society is turning more to softwoods (e.g. shorter lifetime of furniture). All international studies point to an increase of demand for softwoods (solid wood products, but not only), while the demand for hardwoods remains rather low, compared to the potential supply. It is also a matter of prices: hardwoods harvesting, transportation and processing is more costly. Europe is not an island and wood products are a global commodity, with major softwood supplier markets nearby (Russia, North America, South America), so it will not be easy to be competitive. We must be careful not to end up in a situation where we penalise local wood industry”.

- **Socio-economic resilience: New collaborative business models are needed.** The lack of vertical integration is a major weakness. We need to **move from cooperation to real collaboration and integration**, which means building lasting partnerships, joining forest owners and businesses, and creating new businesses models along value chains.

3.3 Recommendations for policymakers

Two main recent EU policies - the Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the European Green Deal - emphasise the need for enhanced resilience of European forest ecosystems through afforestation and restoration (RESONATE Deliverable D5.1). RESONATE recommendations for policymakers proposed several actions that support meeting the goals set by these strategies.

- **Policy needs to ensure effective support systems for forest owners in realising adaptation measures.** These must build on a combination of policy instruments, such as financial support, competence building and increased flexibility of regulations. The systems should provide a long-term, continuous access to support measures which allow a gradual but systemic shift towards the wide adoption of forest resilience in management approaches across Europe.

For national and regional policymakers, “one-size-fits-all” policies are not feasible. EU policies are inherently general and cannot cover all details. However, the varieties and differences of forests, ownerships, regulations, etc. across Europe make local solutions and local policy development/interpretation a necessity.

Financial incentives will be required for most proposed adaptation and restoration measures since the incorporation of resilience and biodiversity measures will make harvesting more costly. Otherwise, it will prove difficult to mobilise owners.

“Resilience silviculture generally costs more. Money becomes available after large disasters for immediate action, but this is only reacting to the problem. Once the crisis fades away, the financial aid is diminishing.”

“There is a large lack of sufficient funding to act and implement these adaptation measures and new management systems.”

Funding through CAP? The amount of funding for forestry has been reduced by half, because the Member States set a higher priority for agriculture. We can learn from the examples how agricultural value chains with small producers (milk, wine, etc) have changed over the past.

“There is a requirement for incentives targeted towards best practice for integrated management. These should be finetuned to prioritise biodiversity.”

“The focus should not just be on incentives/funding, but also on continuous, more structural support and soft measures for forest owners, including forest extension services, education, training and guidelines to enhance knowledge to build up capacity of forest owners in the long term.”

A balanced approach is required. Within public forests the responsibility for conservation is usually placed upon the public owners. However, many municipalities and public estates also depend upon income from timber production.

Small ownership structure is a main challenge: The large number of private owners (including urban forest owners), small size of forest parcels and high number of local forest management associations or producer groups (e.g. several hundred in Bavaria) are a major barrier. This represents an unequal partnership with wood industries, which is a constraint for improved collaboration. Forest owners need to self-organise better and professionalise their activities.

“Best practices of cooperatives must be shared more broadly in Europe, because forest ownership structures are very different across Europe. Example from Aquitaine, France: 30 years ago, they had 100 cooperatives, today there is only one “Alliance Foret-Bois” which now sells 5 million cubic meters. In Sweden and Finland large cooperatives of forest owners and industries exist, but they are missing in the rest of Europe.”

“Other forest products also need collaborative models: In Southern Europe, supplies of main products such as cork, resin or poplar have declined. Therefore, new collaborative organisations have been founded (e.g., Pro-Populus in Italy or Centro Pinus in Portugal) to secure the supply of resources and facilitate the marketing of products.”

- **Policy incentives should promote mixed stands** with suitable species adapted to the projected future climate and site conditions. Following the priorities targeting practice, measures to promote tree diversity, especially **supporting tree species mixture with different functional traits**, are particularly important during the recovery from disturbances to make the next generation of forests better adapted to climate change. Restoration with only fast-growing conifers should not be supported anymore.

National regulations often represent major barriers to work effectively with natural regeneration and effective restoration measures.

There is a flexible/right recovery time window for restoration which should be adapted to local site conditions (climate, soil, flora, fauna). Acting fast is useful to protect microclimate on sites where longer heat waves impact on soils and foster the spread of grass species.

“In the Czech Republic, prolonging forest recovery period has proven useful for state aid financing and to provide more flexibility. But both early and late regeneration measures are being financed.”

- **Subsidies for forest restoration and payments for ecosystem services** can be used to pro-actively increase forest resilience through support to forest owners, who take steps to improve biodiversity, such as maintaining deadwood or *converting monocultures to mixed stands through advance regeneration with diverse species*.

“There is a lack of funds to take on ambitious large-scale restoration efforts and significant preventive action. Effective incentive systems for ecosystem services are also needed.”

“Payments for ecosystem services (PES) should be considered as a potential business model. As in the Spanish example, harvesting companies can create micro-habitats as part of timber extraction operations, through mimicking disturbances.”

- The limited **availability of seeds and nursery material** is a critical problem across the EU. Whereas large state enterprises can maintain their own nursery infrastructure, private and municipal forest owners depend upon the private sector. This should be addressed in national forest regeneration programmes.
- **Information and economic policy instruments** need be developed to **raise awareness** and to **safeguard the socio-economic resilience of forest management**. All stakeholders need to be better informed about the increasing disturbances and adaptation needs in the forest value chain. The risk gap between forest managers and the wood processing industry must be acknowledged: Forest owners, being the first link of the chain, shoulder the biggest burden of the risks and face the highest costs, similarly to small-scale wood processing facilities with limited marketing capacities. At the same time, the mid- to large-scale wood industry, anchored on a higher regional or national level, is more flexible to react, and hence can deal with a delayed risk. Enhanced forest value chain resilience can greatly benefit from streamlining and mainstreaming of adaptation efforts, **promoting partnerships** and encouraging **information exchange across the value chain**.

“Mainstreaming of data, prioritisation of measures, and proper planning will be key.”

“Landscape-level planning tools for risk and resilience are needed: it is very important to address the climate change issue appropriately.”

“Beyond just “mainstreaming” of available information, a dedicated spatially explicit forestry risk assessment as basis for decision-making needs to be build.”

“Possible measures to address the risk gap could include insurance schemes or risk-sharing agreements (such as price guarantees) between forest-owners and wood traders.”

3.4 Recommendations for education and training

How can the adaptation process be enhanced? Enhancing resilience requires also that awareness of climate change and related implications amongst relevant actors is increased. These recommendations are addressed to all concerned actors in the higher education, Vocational Education and Training and lifelong learning domain, including both policymakers, associations / representative bodies and educational professionals to enable them to select and promote resilience enhancing strategies.

- **Providing training support for forest managers**, especially to develop training programs for forest owners on how to manage forests in ways that benefit biodiversity and increase resilience, is very important. The dissemination of best practices in adaptation management with recommendations for different forest conditions should also be promoted via **knowledge transfer** initiatives in national languages, e.g. **via forest extension services**.
- **Higher education / university curricula** in forestry, life sciences and the land use domain need to incorporate knowledge on enhancing forest resilience, dealing with deep uncertainty, and promoting biodiversity to properly equip the next generation of foresters with the required skills. For this purpose, RESONATE developed several resilience modules for university curricula in forest and wood sciences (RESONATE Deliverable D6.9).

- The future forest management will require **better trained, skilled managers and workers**, to make the right decisions about the protection and use of forests and reduce the impacts of harvesting on the ecosystem. Forestry work must be better promoted in order to attract an increased workforce.

i) Training needs for adapting forests

“Greater access to training is an important need, however it is not usually the first priority for small forest owners.”

“Practical, down-to-earth measures are needed so that owners can adopt them relatively easily and easily see the results of their actions.”

“Apply a pragmatic approach on disturbed areas, take practical steps to start the transition to other tree species and change the mindset of forest owners.”

“Private owners need to gain trust to implement it (adaptation). Forest professionals advising landowners must gain a good practical knowledge about forest adaptation to choose and implement measures in the right way.”

“There should be good communication with strong narratives. Owners need to find the messages convincing and to feel confident in any actions that they undertake.”

“Large regional differences in training availability were evident. Whilst there are well established training programmes in some EU countries, these are underdeveloped or missing in other countries.”

ii) Training needs for biodiversity to enhance resilience

“There is a need to raise awareness and to increase knowledge about biodiversity benefits and how to best manage biodiversity (such as through the use of natural regeneration, habitat trees, etc).“

“Knowledge transfer and best practice advice to owners is key for implementing biodiversity measures and for converting forests into protected areas.”

“It is necessary to also provide training to forest owners on their responsibilities regarding risks. This includes proper management of forests so that forest fires don’t get out of control.”

“Raise awareness also for lesser-known topics, like soil restoration or assisted migration.”

iii) Specific points of attention in training

“Available/declining workforce in forestry is a widespread issue. Especially a lack of skilled forest workers who are confident with complex silviculture.”

“Specialist skills are required for forest work in mountainous and/or Mediterranean regions. This applies not only to the nature of terrain involved but also to managing the biodiversity found in these regions.”

“Public sector officials and external professionals, who deal with grants and subsidies, require appropriate training on resilience and biodiversity topics. This will ensure that funds are managed in such a way which optimises their effectiveness.”

Figure 2. Location of the 9 RESONATE case studies across Europe (yellow circles and star).

3.5 Recommendations need to be adopted to the regional context

The **regional context of policy and practice recommendations is crucial**, particularly in the context of enhancing social-ecological resilience. Various statements and recommendations supported by stakeholders confirmed the need to tailor management choices to local needs. RESONATE has addressed such local perspectives in its set of **case study regions** (Figure 2). As an illustration, a few selected examples are presented here to highlight the role of regional specific recommendations:

- **Southern Finland:** Use the time for pro-active management to increase forest resilience to windthrow and bark beetles while disturbance risks are still low. Actions could e.g. include diversifying forest structure and composition and retaining more deadwood, which would also benefit biodiversity policy goals.
- **Ireland:** Future management of Irish forests to facilitate resilience may involve the progressive diversification of species and adoption of alternative silvicultural systems. A gradual restructuring would minimise potential disruption to the current value chains. Adaptive changes and Innovation will be required to ensure industry can take advantage of the new forest structure
- **New Forest, UK:** Forests demonstrated greater resilience to windthrow in areas with low-intensity forest management, suggesting that maintaining this level of management could help preserve ecosystem services.
- **Kostelec, Czech Republic:** Strive for a more balanced approach between direct disturbance control (e.g., salvage and sanitation logging) and efforts to establish climate-adapted resilient forests (e.g. via planting climatically suitable species and controlling game pressure).
- **Upper Rhine Valley, Germany:** intensified forest management with mixtures of climate adapted species, slightly shorter rotation periods and more frequent thinnings can increase resilience to climate change-related disturbances even in forests with high demand for recreation and biodiversity protection.

- **Bauges, France:** Diversify forest composition and structure by promoting the proportion of slow-growing broadleaved species in stands of fast-growing conifers. Use regeneration areas created by disturbance and harvesting as an opportunity to diversify forests, e.g. through natural regeneration.
- **Istria, Croatia:** Maintain the oak coppice forests in the region as these ecosystems successfully provide various ecosystem services, while being resilient to drought.
- **Galicia, Spain:** Encourage cooperative schemes amongst forest owners to address the challenges of fragmented ownership, facilitating the implementation of silvicultural adaptation measures and enhancing disturbance risk management."
- **Catalonia, Spain:** Combine the promotion of more diverse forests with increasing management on overstocked forests.

4 Potential resilience trade-offs and synergies

RESONATE investigated social-ecological resilience across the whole forest value chain and unsurprisingly resilience measures may not always align with each other. Our analysis pointed out some trade-offs that are inevitable because measures that enhance resilience in forest management will have repercussions on the resilience of the forest value chain. Another example is the trade-off between short-term and long-term impacts of management measures affecting resilience that was exemplified in some case study projections - a topic that deserves further investigation.

In general, when we recommend something: “one factor is beneficial for ...” it is important to be transparent about possible trade-off effects for something else (e.g. impacts on biodiversity). Such trade-offs, limitations and structural barriers should be addressed in order to benefit the entire society and not just the forest sector. Limitations and structural barriers were analysed in RESONATE e.g. in Deliverable D2.9 and they are not further analysed here. In the following we discuss some trade-offs that were highlighted in RESONATE research results or pointed out by stakeholders in the RESONATE policy workshop.

4.1 Important issues to be considered in trade-offs

Impact of resilience measures on different ecosystem services

Evidence shows that some species mixtures can be more productive than monospecific forests, but this is not always the case. Planting diverse species, especially mixtures with slow-growing drought tolerant species such as oaks, may lower timber yields and reduce short-term economic gains but builds long-term ecosystem stability (García-Valdés et al., 2021).

Minimising climate change induced risks through intensified thinning and shorter rotation periods is not aligned with the goal to enhance biodiversity (Selwyn et al., 2024) or to maximise carbon storage in forest ecosystems. However, reduced disturbance risks may in the longer-term result in lower carbon releases from large-scale calamities. The management of herbivore populations to mitigate browsing impacts is another example. Browsing poses a risk to tree diversity, as e.g. deer selectively feed on certain species, such as oak. However, herbivores can also play a beneficial role in wildfire-prone areas by reducing fire risk through natural fuel control. Moreover, browsing animals are key in natural forest ecosystem functioning and thereby affecting presence of other species than trees (Trepel et al., 2024). Hence, depending on the purpose of forests, there are conflicting views on how to best control browsing.

Climate change mitigation vs. climate change adaptation

Focussing on carbon sinks in forests may delay necessary adaptation in forest management. Due to limited scientific evidence, the natural or inherent adaptive capacity of unmanaged forests remains a strongly debated topic and different stakeholder groups have conflicting views on the importance of active management in protected areas. Nevertheless, climate change adaptation is essential for long-term effectiveness of climate change mitigation, and this can often be enhanced with active management interventions such as assisted migration.

Conflicting policy perspectives overlap with contrasting resilience measures

Some policy goals are European and decisions in one country are affected by what other countries decide (e.g. GHG emission reduction, bioenergy usage). In such cases, common rules and regulations across Europe are an advantage. But many of the forest adaptation measures are more localised and mainly affect local conditions. Therefore, local conditions dictate the scope of which measures (e.g., species choice, disturbance prevention) are feasible and effective. Uniform strategies carry a risk for failure, and broader European policies always need to be adapted to regional conditions. Over decades, Central-European and Nordic views and management traditions have tended to dominate forest policy debates, but Mediterranean or Eastern countries have also very specific, different needs (e.g. related to regional disturbance regimes) which should be understood and included, allowing for **diverse policy perspectives**.

Inconsistencies and conflicts may occur between European and specific regional/locally policies/approaches. There are multiple conflicts **between sectoral policies** (e.g. between the bioeconomy strategy, which focuses on a circular bioeconomy and fossil fuel replacement, versus the biodiversity strategy, which aims at strict forest protection). In such a context, resilience measures can strongly support one (or several) specific policy objectives such as enhancing forest biodiversity, but they may at the same time also cause trade-offs with other specific policy objectives.

Zoning approaches can facilitate setting priorities and balancing them across the landscape, as many ecosystem services cannot be maximised at the stand level. **Landscape level management** with management objectives tailored to local conditions and with varying intensity of interventions can facilitate an intelligent, balanced combination of contrasting resilience approaches. For example, productive forests managed with frequent interventions to reduce disturbance risks can be combined with extensively managed forests and biodiversity protection in dedicated areas (cf. TRIAD forest management (Nagel et al., 2024)). However, segregating forest areas for different uses is an option that is most easily implemented by large-scale forest owners. In forest areas owned by many small-scale forest owners, zoning approaches would require good coordination and cooperation of a majority of landowners (and their willingness to place common interests over independence in decision-making).

Forest adaptation also needs **adaptive governance** mechanisms to respond to gradually or rapidly changing adaptation challenges. This requires a carefully selected mix of governance instruments at the different levels of governance (EU, member states, regions) to remove implementation barriers (e.g. overregulation, lack of resources, access to information), and better alignment of policy aims to reduce conflicts.

Short-term costs/benefits vs. long-term costs/benefits

Proactive management can be expensive upfront but can reduce future damage. This applies particularly to the conversion of even-aged monocultures. Establishing advanced regeneration is costly but saves regeneration costs later and shortens unproductive periods on disturbed

areas. Managing recently disturbed areas requires resources but is also an opportunity to introduce climate adapted species to make forests more resilient in the future. Particularly costly, but important in production forests, is the protection of admixed species against browsing to develop desirable species mixtures in the regenerating forest.

The opposite effect may also happen, as reducing the rotation period can increase the cash flow in the short term but could have negative effects in the mid- to long-term. Therefore, managing **trade-offs between short- and long-term effects** is a critical challenge of enhancing forest resilience.

Species selection: “Climate-adapted” or native and local genetic material

Tree species selection and choice of provenances are crucial decisions to establish more resilient mixed forests for the future. In the past, huge emphasis was given to the use of “native” (which can be hard to define), “local” species or “natural regeneration”, but with continuous environmental change, these concepts may lose relevance. Insisting on regeneration of only native species, e.g. in Natura 2000 areas, risks maladaptation and increased vulnerability of the coming forest generation. As climate change is altering the suitable range of species, **assisted migration** becomes increasingly important.

Management intensity: Disturbance risks vs biodiversity and carbon sinks

Shorter rotation periods and intensified thinnings are advocated as they have proven to reduce disturbance risks. However, increased management intensity is often harming biodiversity and multifunctionality, requiring careful balancing of trade-offs. It is important to distinguish between management intensity and the timing and frequency of management interventions. In places with high risk, modern silvicultural concepts, earlier thinnings and more frequent interventions should be advocated, yet no drastic change towards short rotation plantations. The rationale is to produce trees with a chosen target diameter in a shorter timescale, when trees are lower in height, to combat risks such as windthrow and drought stress which increase with tree height. Moreover, **integrative forest management** approaches make use of retention trees and dispersed set-aside areas to maintain habitats for biodiversity, which depend upon old trees.

In some regions (e.g. Finland) climate change mitigation policy is also advocating increased stand density and prolonged rotation periods to increase carbon removal in the land use sector. This may conflict with resilience enhancing measures to mitigate disturbance risks. In the long-term, however, disturbance prevention is likely a key to mitigate carbon emissions from the land use sector. Integrative forest management and continuous cover forestry could offer alternative approaches that help minimise these trade-offs.

Disturbance Legacies: Retaining or removing deadwood or biomass

Disturbances increase the abundance of deadwood, which is a crucial habitat for biodiversity. **Retaining deadwood** is thus beneficial for biodiversity, but this may lead to secondary disturbances. For example, bark beetle outbreaks are often triggered by storm or drought disturbances, and deadwood can facilitate their spread. **Sanitation fellings** can mitigate the spread of disturbance agents especially at the beginning of pest outbreaks, but their effectiveness is debated (Hlásny et al., 2021). Some countries have mandatory rules that require sanitation fellings of trees even in protected areas. This may threaten the protection of old-growth forest remnants in Europe, which should be strictly protected. However, completely removing legislation on sanitation fellings is not advisable, especially in wildfire-prone areas, where eliminating the requirement completely could be risky. In the aftermath of bark beetle outbreaks, abundant dead biomass, especially needles and branches, can increase the risk of wildfire. Managing such risks requires zoning approaches, because removal of flammable

biomass is needed specifically at the wildland-urban interface and along public roads. The retention of **deadwood** is useful for biodiversity itself but is also important as a resilience measure. Deadwood can provide an important habitat for **natural predators** which can keep harmful insect populations low.

Potential and limits of natural regeneration

Natural regeneration can play a significant role to increase biodiversity, support the **natural adaptive capacity** of forest ecosystems and facilitate the natural selection of site-adapted genotypes. However, climate-change adapted species or provenances may not be locally present and often cannot naturally migrate fast enough without **assisted migration**. In former monocultures of Norway spruce, natural regeneration often favours spruce again, especially with high game population densities (which is the case in most parts of Europe). Restoring mixed forests with climate-adapted species which fulfil multiple ecosystem service demands, will often require combinations of natural and artificial regeneration.

Access to information can be limiting in different directions

Access to up-to-date monitoring information is crucial to plan pro-active disturbance management measures. Enhancing social-ecological forest resilience requires a thorough understanding of forest conditions, adaptation options in forest management and forest value chain logistics. Researchers invest a lot of time in developing decision support systems to provide evidence-based management recommendations. However, many forest owners and other actors in the value chain are reluctant to give access to data, for various reasons, which weakens the reliability of management guidance.

Trade-offs between adaptation at the beginning and the end of the value chain

There is a likely trade-off in innovation pathways along the wood value chain, where different stages may prioritise conflicting resilience strategies. Early in the chain, adaptation measures focus on diversification of the forest product portfolio through more/different species, mixed structures or mixed management approaches. In contrast, later stages of the wood processing industry are not yet fully committed to adopt this considerable shift and rather focus on adjustments to existing technology or logistics (efficiency, flexibility to react on disturbances). There is trade-off between incremental change in industrial processes and forward-looking adaptive management of whole production systems, including its natural resources base. This misalignment creates a gap in readiness between forest management and industrial processing, potentially weakening overall resilience rather than reinforcing it.

4.2 Synergies between resilience domains exist – not only trade-offs!

Managing social-ecological resilience is a complex decision-making process, as evidenced in the preceding section. But there are not only trade-offs between resilience measures and policy domains - synergies are also possible (cf. Figure 3). Through careful choices and intelligent alignment or combination of measures, it is possible to achieve benefits on multiple fronts at the same time, and this of course would be ideal for various actors from both practice and policy. These can represent optimal, balanced solutions for a given local context, and thereby deserve special attention and consideration for implementation and further research. Such synergies were also highlighted by the policy workshop participants.

Figure 3: Interconnections between the three forest resilience domains investigated in RESONATE. Choices of resilience measures involve both trade-offs (red, dashed lines) and synergies (green lines). An optimal measure reduces trade-offs and maximises simultaneous beneficial synergies, which reinforce overall resilience.

In the RESONATE policy briefs and policy workshop discussions recommendations were developed for these three domains separately. However, this report (chapter 3 and onwards) focuses on the ways they often overlap and interact. For example, increasing biodiversity is a key measure to manage disturbances pro-actively whilst disturbances are increasing biodiversity (in species and structures). More diverse forests are less susceptible to biotic disturbance agents. Moreover, structural diversity is another feature mitigating specific disturbance risks (e.g. from wind). Therefore, several resilience measures proposed in the recommendations will simultaneously benefit biodiversity and disturbance risk mitigation / climate change adaptation.

Measures including some form of management intensification may result in trade-offs between enhanced disturbance resilience and biodiversity. However, integrating them in landscape level strategies and applying the TRIAD approach (Nagel et al., 2024), synergies between these domains are possible, as has been demonstrated in increasingly adopted integrative forest management practices (Aggestam et al., 2020; Konczal et al., 2023).

Another clear synergy exists between disturbance risk management and value chain resilience, as disturbance risk mitigation is also beneficial for value chain resilience. However, possible trade-offs need to be recognised and considered in the implementation of adaptive management approaches. For example, shortened production cycles motivated by harvesting trees with limited tree height to mitigate storm risk do not necessarily have to lead to generally smaller tree dimensions, as early and frequent thinnings can favour diameter growth of the main crop trees.

More challenging is to manage the apparent trade-off between increasing species diversity and the current strong preference of the wood industry for high volume softwood assortments. There is no obvious synergy that could counteract this trade-off, with the exception of sourcing from larger areas. The fact that forest conversion to more diverse resilient forests will be a rather slow process, spanning over several decades could delay the transformation process in the wood industry. The long timespan to transform effectively to these practices should be regarded as an opportunity to become pro-active and to start investing into new technology and new products. This will make the forest industry more resilient in the longer-term, while also opening the potential for making better use of underutilised hardwood resources.

As indicated in Figure 4, some recommendations can simultaneously support biodiversity, the circular bioeconomy and resilience to disturbances. Developing strong synergies for disturbance preparedness, biodiversity enhancement and strengthening value chains, can

provide sizeable opportunities for Europe’s forest-based sector. Pursuing such goals need not be on the same spatial unit. In fact, many studies point at advantages of so-called land sparing rather than land sharing. Moreover, integrative forest management approaches (commonly a land sharing management) nowadays incorporate also protected areas (i.e. land sparing elements). Again, it is however important to consider the specific context – it is unlikely that land sharing or land sparing would be preferable everywhere.

Further research (see also the following chapter 5) should help identify more synergies and better ways of managing the trade-offs identified above.

Figure 4: Identified synergies between measures targeting different resilience domains.

5 Research recommendations

RESONATE advanced research on resilience of social-ecological forest systems. Although many concepts, approaches and solutions have been described, several of the methods employed deserve further development and testing. The operational resilience framework, ORF, has proven very useful in different applications. The next steps to demonstrate its utility should include practical applications in real life decision-making contexts, including active stakeholder engagement as proposed in Nikinmaa et al. (2023). Future research should also explore further trade-offs of resilience-enhancing measures on various ecosystem services and ecological, social or economic resilience indicators.

Investments are required in long-term, integrated resilience research. Forests, wood industries and society are interconnected and the interplay of all drivers, actors, risks and potential solutions must be addressed from a systems point of view to enhance climate resilience. Continuously updated and rigorously researched information is needed across a broad front to support the decision-making of both forest owners and wood industries so they can better adjust to the changing environmental conditions and alleviate rapidly occurring risks both to the environment and economy.

In the project, the concept of looking at societal resilience and the role of forests in this was also introduced. Social-ecological resilience is a promising concept, which allows the integration of resilience in forest management with societal resilience. This should be considered more in the future to support sustainable development in Europe.

A collection of main needs and topics for future research are presented here. These are seen as highly important by the RESONATE Consortium as well as by stakeholders who participated in the RESONATE policy workshop. These topics are recommended for consideration in future European and national research funding programmes.

5.1 Understanding climate change adaptation needs, developing best practice guidance

Climate change affects future species distribution ranges and forest owners and managers need improved guidance on projected changes in site conditions and tree species suitability under different degrees of climatic warming. The climate conditions across European land masses have already warmed substantially more than the global average of +1.3 °C compared to pre-industrial states, with even more drastic changes to climatic extreme events. Consequently, the concept of a static Potential Natural Vegetation (PNV) is no longer useful to guide forest management and nature restoration efforts under climate change. Better process understanding and decision support tools are needed to select tree species and provenances that cope with current and future climate variability over the typical lifespan of trees in managed forests. Specific best practice guidance is needed on:

- Tree species selection and choice of adaptive forest management approaches to deal with risks and climate change: which species and silvicultural systems for which local site?
- How to determine whether species are no longer sufficiently climate-adapted – and how to respond in forest management?
- What are suitable and economically viable approaches to increase tree species diversity and convert monocultures into mixed resilient forests to distribute risks? Here, more information is needed on most suitable combinations of tree species.

- Economic analysis of proactive management to deal with future uncertainties
- Hotter droughts (and associated disturbances) are likely to become an important driver of forest dynamics in many areas: identifying trait combinations and forest structures that promote resilience to drought should be a priority.
- Forest managers often do not have any previous experience with restoring extensive disturbed areas exposed to extreme climate conditions combined with other stresses, such as browsing by herbivores. So, how should best use be made of disturbed areas across Europe to adapt tree species composition to forthcoming climate change and future disturbance regimes? Scientific guidance and best practice examples are needed to inform post-disturbance recovery, including species selection.
- Further research is needed on assisted migration and assisted gene flow to support forest adaptation to climate change in Europe. This requires improved understanding of regeneration options, combining natural and artificial regeneration, as newly admixed species or genotypes will require decades before they start to reproduce and regenerate naturally. Consequently, the genetic population will require assisted gene flow over extended periods of time. Improved guidance is also needed to manage the risks involved and ensuring ecological compatibility, resilience, and long-term sustainability of enriched genetic diversity. For example, science-based thresholds for proportions of non-native species to avoid negative effects on biodiversity are urgently needed.
- Natura2000 sites: In cases, where it is clear that the current habitat type will likely not persist under projected climate change, solutions are required how to develop these habitat types, for example through active enrichment with adapted native tree species. In more extreme conditions, solutions may be required to transition existing habitat types to different future habitat types, e.g. from a European beech to an oak dominated forest.

More experimentation is needed to better understand climate change adaptation on different and changing site conditions. Monitoring does not substitute the lack of process understanding and empirical evidence that prevents wider uptake of best practices.

5.2 Natural adaptive capacity of trees and forest ecosystems

Almost all European forests have been managed more or less intensively over many centuries. The adaptive capacity of unmanaged protected forest areas is not well understood, because forest reserves are generally small and widely affected by humans (e.g. through air pollution or (lack of) management of regional ungulate game populations). Better understanding the adaptive capacity of natural areas is important to anticipate extinction risks of rare species and to assess, by means of developing criteria, when active adaptation such as assisted migration is desirable to enhance resilience of forests and sustain their service provisioning.

- Genetic diversity of forest stands is strongly affected by past management and the origin of forest reproductive materials. Drought sensitivity varies genetically within tree populations, but it is unclear whether and how genetic monitoring could be used to support climate change adaptation.
- Epigenetic adaptation of trees to drought is not well understood.

5.3 Enhancing resilience through biodiversity – how to do it?

Biodiversity has been identified as a crucial measure to enhance resilience of forest ecosystems. Mixed forests consisting of species with complementary functional traits have shown increased resilience to disturbances compared to monocultures. Enhanced structural diversity and soil biodiversity support the functioning of terrestrial ecosystems and their delivery of ecosystem services. There are multiple benefits of biodiversity, but knowledge on how diverse species or species communities can be used to actively enhance resilience is still limited. Conversion from even-aged monocultures to resilient structurally diverse mixed forests is a slow process.

- Meaningful, quantifiable indicators for local level decision making: Deadwood volume or number of retention trees in forests is much lower in managed forests than certain endangered species require. Target indicator values or minimum thresholds would give forest owners a reference to know how much effort is needed to achieve a certain goal. Ranges for indicator target values could be used to distinguish different levels of ambition. Such reference values are currently not yet established.
- Forest management approaches sensitive to biodiversity, such as continuous cover forestry (CCF) or close to nature forestry (CNF), etc. are already practiced in many parts of Europe. Yet they are often reliant on experiential knowledge. The value and relevance of this knowledge is eroding rapidly with climate change. Thus, we need to develop a more mechanistic understanding of the influence of forest structure and composition on ecosystem functioning under the conditions of global change. Evidence-based indicators are needed that are useful for forest managers and can be harnessed for policy goals.
- How can biodiversity be made attractive to foresters and landowners? Can financial incentives be a tool to promote biodiversity and how should they be designed to avoid leakage? Should financial incentives follow an input approach (paid before intervention) or an output approach (paid after intervention)?
- What are the real costs? A better understanding of economic versus environmental balance is needed, especially for rural communities. It is necessary to look deeper into regional cases where higher biodiversity also has led to stable or higher economic returns.

5.4 Disturbance risk management: put more focus on enhancing resilience!

The crisis or disaster risk management cycle includes four phases: disturbance response, disturbance recovery, disturbance prevention, and preparation to handle future disturbances. In the past, the main focus was put on disturbance response, for example how to detect and rapidly extinguish forest fires or suppress pest outbreaks. Disturbance recovery was often done without considering the need of increased forest resilience, for example through replanting spruce monocultures after wind disturbances or bark beetle outbreaks. Considering the climate change induced intensification of forest disturbances, it is of paramount importance to increase efforts in holistic disturbance risk management, embracing the entire risk management cycle. This starts with designing disturbance recovery with increased forest resilience and disturbance prevention in mind. There are many knowledge gaps how to enhance society's social-ecological resilience to live with intensified disturbance regimes. Disturbances are a natural driver of forest ecosystem dynamics, and it is not realistic nor desirable to prevent all disturbances. However, we need to collect best practice experiences on how to manage our forests to counteract the climate-change induced increased frequency

and intensity of forest disturbances. Also the forestry sector should build capacity to anticipate and prepare to handle future disturbances.

- There is very little research on holistic disturbance management considering all four phases of the risk management cycle. Wildfire risk prevention needs to be conceived and implemented through management at the landscape (or even regional) scale.
- New pests and disease risks: Research and monitoring has historically focused on a limited number of prominent forest pests and diseases. However, with climate change, less prominent pests and diseases, which were previously considered harmless, can increase their activity, or previously resilient tree species can emerge vulnerable. How to prepare for new threats?
- Browsing control: Science-based groundwork, improved dialogue and communication to design better policies are essential to tackle this highly conflictual topic. There is a need to resolve the conflict between game management and forest adaptation objectives to prevent damage to forest regeneration and allow diversification. On the other hand, in wildfire-prone areas, a controlled level of browsing by herbivores (wild or domestic animals) may help improve fuel control.
- Better understanding is needed on disturbance interactions and the importance of legacies of past disturbances.

5.5 Social and socio-economic resilience

The uptake of resilience enhancing measures is strongly dependent on social acceptance and socio-economic factors. More research is needed into better understanding constraints and social dynamics, for example on the relationship between conservation goals, productivity and forest resilience. Socio-economic resilience is not yet well understood. Private forest owners have so far relied strongly on the economic value of wood production to sustain their business. The role of forests for societal resilience is little understood. There is a need for a real economic evaluation of disturbance impacts and resilience measures. Increased disturbance frequency and intensity puts the economic viability of forest management which relies on wood production at risk. More evidence is needed to identify which risks might potentially result in which short and longer-term impacts and how resilience enhancing measures should be distributed over high risk or low risk areas.

- Economic evaluation/impact assessment of adaptation for resilience: What are the total private and public costs and benefits of implementing the different proposed resilience measures? And how are they likely to be distributed between actors? What does it mean in different regions? Which are the risks and effects on the enterprise level, which on a regional level?
- Cost-benefit analysis including both marketed and non-marketed goods and services: Advanced models should be developed to quantify the costs and benefits of resilience measures across various industries and value chains. For example, who carries the biggest burden of costs and who has most of the benefits? How can such imbalances be addressed and mitigated?
- Can diversified ecosystem service portfolios based on payment for ecosystem services (PES), subsidies from state/regional authorities, or others make forest owners less dependent on income from wood production?

- Valuation of biodiversity outcomes: Biodiversity affects both marketed and non-marked values. What are the total costs and benefits of biodiversity loss – and conservation? Which policy instruments can be used to safeguard biodiversity? How can the complexity of biodiversity better be included in natural capital accounting, so that consistency between countries and typologies are secured?
- Demand resilience is not properly understood yet. Experiences in the context of climate-smart agriculture suggest that the integration of demand management strategies could increase societal resilience. So far, only limited attention has been given to demand-led resilience measures in the forest-based sector or concerning climate-smart forestry– this deserves more research efforts.

5.6 Develop the knowledge base for adaptation

A widely supported recommendation from stakeholders is to invest in long-term, integrated resilience research. There is a need to understand the interactions, risks and synergies from forestry to value chains and how resilience adaptation and innovation can support the transformation. Building on such improved process understanding, regional solutions are needed to adopt suitable measures to the local conditions.

a) Improving decision support tools and research infrastructure

Future development of forest resources remains uncertain due to unknown future policy priorities affecting Greenhouse-Gas-Emissions reductions, limited understanding of changing extreme climatic events and remaining gaps in physiological process understanding of tree responses to climate warming and increased disturbance frequency and intensity. The majority of forest simulation models are overpredicting CO₂ fertilisation effects and cannot yet realistically represent extreme climate events and disturbance impacts. Reliable decision support requires:

- Improved forest simulation models with efficient model intercomparison and model synthesis schemes that can improve projections of forest landscape dynamics under changing climate and disturbance regimes
- Investments in and coordination of long-term forest research infrastructure, including experiments that deliberately target current uncertainties in tree responses to extreme climatic events and their representation in models (e.g., impacts of intensified droughts or the level and persistence of the CO₂ fertilisation effect)
- Improved data and information infrastructure with open access to experiment results, including sufficient meta-data to allow inclusion in meta-analysis. This also requires training of scientists to develop their studies and publications in a format that is conducive for synthesis.

b) Monitoring and use of monitoring information to support decision-making

Many initiatives aim to improve access to forest monitoring data (e.g. EU forest monitoring directive). National forest inventory data remains the most important data source on national forest resources, but they need to be complemented with data from remote sensing and specialised inventories (e.g. on biodiversity indicators) to provide spatially explicit forest observation with higher temporal resolution to inform e.g. about tree vitality, disturbance impacts and other resilience-relevant measures. Furthermore, development of PES could be an incentive to manage forests for climate change mitigation. This necessitates carbon stock and sink monitoring for climate change mitigation policies. Monitoring, including both mid-term

and near real-time schemes, provides the best source of evidence to ground-truth our 'process understanding'. What needs further development is the integration of monitoring data with decision-support tools.

- Near real-time monitoring: Design and implement real-time monitoring systems to assess resilience and support proactive decision-making during disruptions.
- Inform pro-active disturbance risk management with remote sensing data, e.g. detecting vulnerable trees besides critical infrastructure, mapping areas for grazing or prescribed burning to manage flammable biomass, detecting biotic disturbances.
- Develop regular socio-economic monitoring of forest owners and users to complement forest ecosystem monitoring and thus facilitate a more complete understanding of decision making in forest social-ecological systems.
- Processing measurements into guidance for decision makers: new remote sensing technology and sensors are continuously developed and should be better exploited. Users in forestry practice cannot handle huge amounts of data and thus require processed service products to support decision-making.
- Regeneration monitoring: How can this be done effectively and efficiently and how can it be supported by remote sensing approaches? Forest regeneration models so far provide poor predictions of regeneration density and species composition. An effective combination of modelling and monitoring is required to guide regeneration following disturbances.
- Data quality and streamlining of value chain data: Improve regional data quality and streamline reporting frameworks to better integrate with state-level and European reporting frameworks (e.g., align with EUDR). This should include comprehensive pricing data for various wood assortments and key industry-specific operational parameters, such as road infrastructure details.
- DNA-based tree species identification tool: There is a need for law enforcement in international and European timber trade. The aim is to develop a credible, fast test method to determine if a tree species is strictly protected or legal to be traded. Illegal timber trade is a threat to the socio-economic resilience of the domestic wood industry. Better traceability and data-driven control over origins of timber is essential to close gaps and build stronger links in regional value chains, notably also to develop new hardwoods-based markets.

c) Science-policy-practice interface: Implementation gap

Knowledge on resilience enhancing measures needs to reach practitioners: best practices need to be shared better within and across regions. What are the real reasons behind why forest owners refrain from forest adaptation and conversion? Many complex limitations and barriers need to be better understood. Better guidance is needed to support decisions that are dealing with uncertain future conditions, e.g. what to plant or how to manage species mixtures.

- Develop capacity building modules for extension services on enhancing forest resilience in forest management.
- Explore how policies impact the resilience of forest value chains, with a particular focus on trade-offs between the biodiversity strategy and the bioeconomy strategy.

5.7 Managing resilience trade-offs

Different measures have been identified to help enhance resilience in forest management or complete forest value chains. Some of these align well with each other, whereas others can also lead to trade-offs. We need better tools to manage trade-offs in forest management, between ecosystem service demands of society, and across policy domains. A holistic assessment of social-ecological resilience can integrate many of these aspects, but more research is needed to better understand and find solutions for managing such trade-offs.

- Short-term vs long-term resilience benefits: Some measures affect resilience in different ways in the short- versus the long-term. For example, forest conversion to resilient mixed forests takes time and may require interventions that increase short-term disturbance risks before yielding positive impacts. How can such short-term trade-offs be mitigated? Transparent communication about contrasting impacts of resilience measures is important also to secure support from stakeholders.
- Protection versus production: The Biodiversity strategy talks a lot about protection, but Resonate recommendations target also active measures to increase biodiversity, e.g. through integrative forest management and restoration practices targeting increased forest resilience. Clear concepts and common language are needed to implement climate and biodiversity smart forest management approaches, combining protected areas and actively managed forests.
- Public opinion on biodiversity: What does the public want for “their” public forests? How to communicate to the public, unpopular management decisions which aim at mid- or long-term increased resilience and reduced disturbance impacts?

5.8 Research on forest value chains, wood industry, socioeconomics

Forest value chains and the wood industry need to adapt to the changing climate and intensified disturbance regimes. Transport infrastructure is a critical bottleneck in the processing of large amounts of salvage timber following big disturbances. How should industry adapt to changes in wood supply and assortments and deal with underused and less favoured tree species/hardwoods, to create valuable products? In the future, through innovation, wood industries should be enabled to use all sorts of wood resources. Transport costs will become critical in the case of local forest resource scarcity (e.g. softwood in regions devastated by bark-beetles, or valuable species but with low regional marketable volumes). Wider systemic understanding, in turn, is needed for forward-looking adaptive management of the whole production system, including anticipation of the incremental change in industrial processes and the timescale of the natural resource base that the particular value chain or wood industry is dependent on.

- Optimise harvest and transport logistics to get better prepared for future large-scale disturbances. Spatial optimisation of wood storage infrastructure, improving the flexibility of railway transport and increasing its capacity. How should wood supply chains be networked with varying wood quality, etc.?
- Adapt harvesting technology to improve economic and environmental efficiency across a wider gradient of technological conditions, e.g., to better cope with warmer winters and unfrozen soil conditions. This should enable the use of fully mechanised harvesting systems for hardwoods and improve the operational efficiency when processing disturbances.

- Design technologies that streamline information sharing between value chain actors to improve tactical and operational planning and decision making.
- Develop and promote processing technologies with improved flexibility of input qualitative parameters, such as quality grade or species to increase the harvesting timber yield and to foster the cascading use of timber and maximise the added value throughout its multiple uses.
- Research the possibilities of improving the efficiency of the biomass trade and logistics through effective commoditisation.
- Systemic understanding is needed on the interlinkages between the regional, national and international outlook on the social-ecological resilience of forest value chains. In other words, analysis in terms of the local perspective on the resilience of forest value chains, should be extended to focus on observing further stages in the value chains, ideally in their entirety. Furthermore, alternative scenarios should be co-produced with the key stakeholders, connecting both local and global scale, in order to test the adaptive capacity of a value chain vis-a-vis the changing operating environment.

5.9 The role of forest owners in wood markets challenged by climate change

Increasing disturbances and risks makes smallholder forestry even less viable and more and more urban forest owners lose interest in their forest, or value other functions higher than wood production. What happens when forest owners step out of the market? What is the role of cultural values and the attachment to the land? How is it possible to approach and motivate such forest owners? What are the consequences for wood supply and markets?

- A holistic view of the value chains and their interplay of actors and stakeholders must be investigated, connecting forest owners, managers, processing industries and end users of products/services, to better understand the socio-economic dimension of forest resilience and integrate it into risk management and support instruments.
- Land abandonment: More and more forest owners stop actively managing their forests. This is already a major factor in Southern Europe and will become an even more severe problem with growing disturbances in other European regions. Understanding motivational as well as structural and governance drivers of this abandonment is needed to be able to develop strategies and solutions which are urgently needed.
- Small-scale owner behaviour: It is necessary to further understand the behaviour and objectives of small-scale forest owners to anticipate future trends. For example,
 - Further investigation of the observation that forest owners might have monetary objectives, whilst only a few prioritise profit maximisation.
 - Further investigate groups that operate with little-to-no profit orientation.

5.10 A systemic, sectoral approach to the hardwoods question: linking resilience with innovation

How should the paradoxical situation of diminishing softwoods and large underused resources of hardwoods, with almost no market, be addressed? Today 60-80% of hardwoods are used directly as fuelwood and bioenergy or are exported as raw timber to other countries. It is expected and recommended that even more hardwoods will be grown in our future forests. This is a key question for today's entire forest-based sector. It represents a systemic challenge

where a more forward-looking approach will be needed to improve the adaptive capacity of the entire production system.

- A broader narrative and ambition for forests and industry is needed: The forest-based bioeconomy is a true domestic industry with a high innovation potential, that relies on sustainable forest management as precondition and can deliver on decarbonisation and substitution. It is fully in line with the EU priorities but needs to be better connected to the new industrial policies and the competitiveness from a systemic perspective.
- Dialogue between forest owners and industry needs to be strengthened to find a common ground between both sides, because both depend on each other. A difficulty is that industry plans usually some 10 to 15 years ahead but not longer, whereas forestry takes a much longer time horizon in perspective. Industries are also reluctant to change anything as long as softwood supplies in their region are still abundant.
- Broad, forward-looking analysis and technological foresight on materials science advances are needed to understand the new uses and value chains. Together with the wood industry, technology suppliers and potential customer industries can exploit game-changing innovation in solid wood products from hardwoods.

R&I on more efficient and new harvesting and processing technology is needed for hardwoods. Hardwoods are heavier than softwoods and require different equipment such as trailers, skidders, trucks and adapted, or new, sawmill equipment. Modern harvesters are designed for softwoods but cannot process most hardwoods. New harvesting systems must also be cost-effective to deal with smaller volumes and ensure low environmental impacts.

- New uses and value chains might offer the solution: Softwoods have more uniform growth patterns, resulting in a high share of stem wood. In comparison, hardwoods are a much more heterogeneous resource (e.g., more branches and bark, higher variability of wood qualities). In addition, the shift to more hardwood will be likely accompanied with increasing tree species diversity. Hence, further wood processing streams need to be able to accommodate a heterogeneous resource base. Novel uses such as biochar, bioplastics, textiles or biorefinery products offer potential opportunities, but are mostly still under development and not yet sufficiently competitive for upscaling. More support for R&I and demonstration is needed, e.g. under the CBE-JU programme.
- Research with industry is key to exploit innovation in solid wood products from hardwoods: Wood industries and machine manufacturers are focussing on incremental innovation of established technologies, yet only little R&D activity addresses the systemic challenges, which may require more disruptive innovation. There is also a common gap between plentiful research results financed through national and EU funding, but very limited uptake and actual exploitation of results by companies in the market. More support for R&I and demonstration is needed, e.g. under CBE-JU programme and EIT.
- Cascading principle, resource efficiency, circular use: We must address the question of what the sustainability limits of multifunctional forest supply are, given the growing demand for many new uses and the need not externalise problems by increasing imports to Europe on a large scale. People overestimate the supply capacity of forests. Resource efficiency must be the main goal, to optimise consumption according to the cascading principle and to also develop circular uses of wood. Wood construction is booming and it's possible to already find innovations such as design-for-disassembly solutions (e.g. new joints and connectors, built-in sensors), although the main engineered wood products used (CLT, GLT) are not circular per se. Because of its complexity, this challenging topic should be a key priority for research,

6 Conclusions

RESONATE investigated how resilience can be enhanced in social-ecological forest systems. It covered a broad range of topics ranging from ecosystem processes (e.g. on the importance of biodiversity for resilient forest ecosystems) to forest management interventions (e.g. thinning and tending), forest harvesting, transport of products to processing facilities, production and consumption of forest-based products and services and possible changes in demand.

Many different recommendations have been identified based on the scientific evidence developed in the project. Feedback from stakeholders on these recommendations showed that they are all relevant – some more pressing and uniformly supported than others. Discussion groups in a RESONATE policy workshop organised in Brussels ranked the importance of measures to enhance resilience, which were synthesised in this report with different target groups in mind.

One overarching recommendation is the importance of adapting measures to the local context. Growth conditions and disturbance regimes vary, and climate change is affecting forests differently depending on location across Europe. There cannot be a one-size-fits-all policy or management recommendations that are generally applicable across all forest types and socio-economic circumstances. Accordingly, recommendations presented in this report should always be checked for their feasibility for implementation under the local conditions and adapted as needed to the economic and social realities.

The discussion of resilience trade-offs and synergies showed that enhancing diversity is not only serving biodiversity, but also a key measure to enhance resilience to disturbances. Moreover, landscape level measures and planning approaches are essential to manage trade-offs and optimise disturbance risk prevention. Conversion of softwood monocultures (which are often highly susceptible to disturbances) into climate and biodiversity smart mixed stands is strongly recommended to make forests more resilient to climate change and disturbances and to sustain their ecosystem service provisioning under changing conditions.

This transition will take time, but eventually it will lead to very different resource supply conditions for the wood industry. Diversifying wood assortments will challenge strategies in the wood industry that were optimised for efficiency in the past, relying mostly on large volumes of uniform softwood qualities. The recommendations targeting enhanced resilience in the forest value chain, represent an opportunity for the sector to embrace innovation and make better use of hardwoods which are currently often under-utilised and as low added-value products.

RESONATE clearly advanced the state of knowledge on forest resilience. However, there is a huge implementation gap remaining. Thus, a set of important recommendations targeted how to improve knowledge transfer, support the shift from disturbance response to disturbance prevention and enable improved capacities to enhance resilience, not only in forest management, but also in the complete forest value chain.

RESONATE developed innovative methods and approaches to assess social-ecological resilience. But further development and application of methods is needed. A widely supported recommendation from stakeholders is to invest in long-term, integrated resilience research. This is particularly true for the assessment of forest value chain resilience and the development of pro-active adaptation strategies within the forest sector.

More collaborative Research & Innovation is needed to bridge the risk gap between forest managers and the industry, to find local solutions addressing the climate risks/production/protection trade-offs. This should support the transition from softwood dominance to more

diverse wood assortments before climate change induced shortages in softwoods become a widespread reality for the forest-based sector.

Both policy makers and practitioners favour pro-active measures in managing forest disturbances and enhancing forest resilience. However, the topic of forest value chain resilience is not yet on the radar of most decision-makers and funding organisations. There is a need to understand the interactions, risks and synergies from forestry to value chains and how resilience adaptation and innovation can support the transformation. Building on the general insights from RESONATE, recommendations need to be applied and tested in diverse local conditions to develop a portfolio of best practices. The new FoRISK facility established by the pan-European high-level forest policy process Forest Europe could play a significant role to facilitate trans-border knowledge sharing of such best practices in disturbance risk management. Their effectiveness needs to be monitored to enable further adjustments, to ensure cost-effectiveness as precondition to wide uptake in practice.

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8 Annex

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RESONATE

Resilient Forests for Society

Rooting for Resilience

RESONATE Final Policy Workshop - Summary Report

Date: 31/03/2025

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Coordinator: ²European Forest Institute (EFI)

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Executive Summary

Climate change is a long-term challenge affecting both forest ecosystems and forest-based value chains. Solutions for adapting forests to increasing disturbances and ecosystemic shifts must address the issue in a holistic manner. The RESONATE project has delivered a broad base of research findings on forest resilience concepts, trends, case studies and proposed applicable solutions for practitioners and decision-makers. The team also published three policy briefs addressing recommendations how to better manage disturbances, biodiversity and value chain resilience.

The final policy workshop in Brussels offered a forum to experts of the European Commission, public and private forest owners, industries, NGOs and other interest groups to jointly reflect with the researchers on the relevance of the project for EU forest policy processes. This report documents in detail the setup and outcomes of the workshop.

The European Commission was represented with five Directorates-General (DG): DG Climate Action, DG Environment, DG Research and Innovation, DG Agriculture, and DG GROW (Industry). The EC policy officers delivered brief statements about ongoing and upcoming policy initiatives of the different DGs and confirmed that RESONATE's research results are well aligned with them.

The participants discussed the policy briefs in three separate groups. They gave plenty of comments, examples and suggestions, and validated most of the recommendations. The dialogue provided valuable feedback regarding the relevance and level of priority of the recommendations, pointing out important perspectives from different stakeholder groups and forest regions across Europe.

The impulse talks and statements given by the speakers, and the detailed contributions of participants contributed to shaping the recommendations and further research needs. The interactive workshop format proved suitable to collect many relevant impulses to address forest resilience and adaptation in policy design and implementation on national and regional level.

Keywords

Resilience, policy, forest ecosystem, forest management, biodiversity, bioeconomy, value chains, stakeholder engagement

1 Introduction

1.1 Project context and workshop objectives

Climate change is gaining attention in public awareness, but the tremendous impacts on our forests, and the need to increase the resilience of forests and related value chains through adaptation and novel management practices is less known and insufficiently displayed. Proper guidance and decision tools for forest owners and managers, policy makers and the wood-based industry are not available or well accessible.

The RESONATE project, coordinated by the European Forest Institute from 2021 to 2025, has addressed this gap of knowledge through collaborative research of 20 partner institutions from 12 European countries. The project aims to strengthen the resilience of forest ecosystems and forest value chains to adapt to climate change and increased disturbances harnessing a variety of management measures, providing best practice examples and tailor-made solutions to all stakeholder target groups.

“Forest disturbances are making headlines, but we need better guidance how to increase resilience of our forests and help the forest sector adapt to climate change. Building resilient forests goes beyond trees: it requires robust value chains and engaging communities for a sustainable future. Proper advice to enhance forest value chain resilience are still lacking.”

Marcus Lindner, EFI, project coordinator

The RESONATE policy workshop was organised in Brussels, 10th of February 2025. It has been designed for policy actors, decision-makers and experts in forest ecosystems, forest management and forest-based industries across Europe. The purpose was to engage directly with European Commission staff from relevant DGs, European advocacy groups and national representatives and provide a platform to jointly reflect on their relevance of the results for EU forest policy processes.

The specific objectives of the workshop were:

- i) To inform about the key results and policy findings of the project,
- ii) To discuss the role of these findings within the wider European policy context: What is their importance? What else needs to be considered?
- iii) To synthesise main policy recommendations and research needs addressed by the key target groups: How can resilience knowledge and solutions be adopted, be further developed, and be mainstreamed in European forest management?

This report provides a full documentation of the policy workshop and the contributions of the participants. It summarizes the feedback of the European stakeholders and expert views, to complement the main final reports of the project, notably D5.5 ‘Synthesis report on integrated resilience assessment’ and D5.6 ‘Policy recommendations for improving forest resilience’.

1.2 Workshop setup

1.2.1 Design and execution

The organisational team of InnovaWood, EFI and Prospex Institute held regular online meetings to jointly develop the workshop concept, prepare the setup and programme, and implement the workshop according to the following steps (Table 1).

Table 1 Steps and timeline of policy workshop design

No.	Activity	Meeting, date
1.	Initial concept proposal to the consortium	Project meeting Copenhagen, Denmark, on 13-15 March 2024
2.	Work sessions on synthesis of results and policy recommendations	Final consortium meeting in Bonn, Germany, 28-29 Nov 2024
3.	Announcement and invitations to stakeholder target groups	Mailing and social media (LinkedIn), December 2025
4.	Writing and publication of policy briefs	January 2025
5.	Pre-meetings/ briefings with invited speakers	Online, January 2025
6.	Policy workshop	Brussels, 10 February 2025
7.	Documentation and workshop report	February to March 2025

1.2.2 Workshop agenda and method

The policy workshop itself was carried out in three parts (cf. agenda in Annex chapter 7.2, Table 6). In the first part, the participants were introduced to the workshop objectives and practicalities. They were informed that the workshop is carried out according to Chatham House Rule¹, and that the workshop report does not reveal the persons' identities. The workshop has been audio recorded for documentation purposes only.

The RESONATE's main findings and three policy briefs were presented by members of the project team. Then followed five impulse talks by EC policy officers and regional representatives, to set the scene of the European policy context.

In the second part of the workshop, the participants were split up into three parallel groups held in separate rooms. Each discussion group was facilitated by two RESONATE team members and focused on a different topic. Each group addressed the following questions:

a) Recommendations

- *Priorities*: Which of the RESONATE recommendations in the policy briefs are the most important and impactful from your stakeholder perspective?
- *Relevance & Constraints*: How useful are these recommendations for your work, and which challenges do you see to implement them?
- *Going further*: Which additional recommendations can you propose, expanding the scope of forest resilience to the wider EU policy context?

¹ The Chatham House Rule is used around the world to encourage inclusive and open dialogue in meetings. It reads: "When a meeting, or part thereof, is held under the Chatham House Rule, participants are free to use the information received, but neither the identity nor the affiliation of the speaker(s), nor that of any other participant, may be revealed." Source: <https://www.chathamhouse.org/about-us/chatham-house-rule>

b) Research needs

- Where do you see a lack of usable information for decision support on forest resilience?
- Which topics should be tackled by future research?

For defining priorities, the participants were asked to choose the recommendations which they consider of highest relevance. They communicated their choice by marking three selected recommendations on a poster printout using colour dot stickers. The prepared stickers had a colour code which allowed to distinguish the priority voting per the five target groups (cf. Table 3, Table 4, Table 5).

Regarding the other questions, participants noted down their contributions on Post-Its, which were collected and arranged on flipcharts. The moderators guided the discussion, during which the participants could highlight their important points, provide further explanations to their arguments and react on statements by the other participants.

For the third part of the workshop, the participants reunited in the plenary room, and the moderators delivered a short summary of each group session. In a panel discussion, the RESONATE team members then reflected more on the outcomes and important aspects highlighted by the participants.

To close the workshop, the RESONATE coordinator offered some final conclusions, and thanked all participants for their valuable contributions (Annex chapter 7.4).

1.2.3 Attendance

The workshop was well attended by 40 persons, of which 25 represented the target groups of stakeholders that were invited to actively contribute (Figure 1, Table 2). The participants revealed a balanced gender distribution and fair geographical representation of European countries. A large share of the participants is based in Brussels, as they represent both the EC and European associations or interest groups.

The list of represented organisations can be found in Annex chapter 7.1.

Figure 1 Workshop participants statistics

Table 2 Workshop attendance per group of participants

Group	Count
Resonate team (researchers, role as facilitators)	12
EC representatives (main target group A)	10
European and national stakeholders (target groups B – E)	15
Additional observers (passive role)	3
Gender distribution	21 female, 19 male
Geographical distribution (acc. to the organisations' focus)	21 EU / international, 7 EU countries
Participants in total	40
Total stakeholders (as active contributors, A – E)	25

1.3 Key research findings and introduction to policy briefs

RESONATE, a four-year project of a large European consortium, has produced a broad range of research results, which are published in many scientific papers and project deliverable reports. A summary of key findings was given by lead coordinator Marcus Lindner in his opening presentation (cf. Annex chapter 7.3).

The main topics of relevant knowledge gaps and policy needs have been addressed in three policy briefs (Lindner et al. 2025, Schifferdecker et al. 2025, Hoeben et al. 2025).

Topic 1. Disturbance management. Proactive risk assessment and prevention e.g., against bark beetle outbreaks or forest fires, is becoming a top priority for forest managers. Guidance by policymakers and experts needs to build on holistic European assessment data and monitoring tools to then establish regionally adapted strategies fit for implementation by land managers and forest practitioners.

Topic 2. Biodiversity plays a crucial role in enhancing forest resilience and adaptability under climate change and increased disturbances. Forests with diverse tree species are better equipped to withstand and recover from extreme weather events, boosting both their ecological stability and productivity. Disturbances can create opportunities to introduce climate-adapted species and enhance biodiversity.

These three policy briefs were the basis for the policy workshop, which served to gain feedback from key policy stakeholders.

Topic 3. Value chain resilience. There is a general lack of awareness and unpreparedness of market actors and stakeholders in the forest-based value chains regarding the scale of climate change on forests, and their effects on forest products and ecosystem services. Potential impacts and needs must be better understood by all actors to adapt and to innovate, which requires more collaborative efforts and coordination.

Figure 2 Impressions from the RESONATE Policy Workshop in Brussels: views of the audience, moderators, panel discussion, and networking during coffee breaks

2 Impulse talks and contributions by EC Policy Officers

2.1 DG Climate Action statement

Peter Löffler, Policy Officer, [European Commission, Directorate-General for Climate Action \(DG CLIMA\)](#), Adaptation and Resilience to Climate Change Unit.

His work focuses on climate adaptation and health, the [European Climate and Health Observatory](#), adaptation in forestry, biodiversity, and nature conservation policies. He also collaborates on the Climate-ADAPT knowledge platform with the [European Environment Agency \(EEA\)](#).

- The first ever [European Climate Risk Assessment](#) was published in 2024. It identified 36 critical risks related to climate change and shows that they are growing rapidly.
- An ambitious [European Climate Adaptation Plan](#) is now being developed to ensure that these risks will be properly addressed. A policy package will be produced by the second half of 2026 and prepare also relevant legislation in the field. It is being accompanied by a proper impact assessment and appropriate consultation measures.
- The plan will be an integrated governance approach involving a many Commissioners who have a remit to support this ambitious adaptation plan. The goal is that it works across the board and all the services of the EC, and in conjunction with the [Competitiveness Compass](#). The plan will address three dimensions:
 - *People*: livelihoods, well-being, health, life expectancy, wealth and economic security.
 - *Natural resources*: safeguarding their continuity and provision of ecosystem services.
 - *Climate change as an economic menace*: resilience and preparedness are now framed in the competitiveness and prosperity context, i.e. prevention of losses, protection of assets and economic resilience, but also potential market opportunities for products and services which enhance resilience.
- Forest related issues and topics come much into play for all three pillars, as they are very relevant with respect to natural resources and provision of ecosystem services.
- Governance will be a main pillar, such as risk ownership and responsibilities for managing the adaptation policy cycle, and forest adaptation is part of the picture.
- Finance is the second pillar. Resilience by design must be integrated into all future financial frameworks and budgeting, including mobilising private finance providers and insurance. Resilience is a key element of the future [European Finance Adaptation Plan](#).
- RESONATE results have a lot of good substance, which is very relevant for these adaptation plans, and should be contributed to this process.

2.2 DG Environment statement

Stefanie Schmidt, Policy Officer for Forests, European Commission Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV).

She works on the [EU Forest Strategy 2030](#), with a focus on closer-to-nature forestry, and is involved in biodiversity-related policies, including the [EU Biodiversity Strategy](#) and the [Taxonomy Regulation](#). With a background in natural sciences, environmental policy, and sustainability, she has held various roles in and outside the EC.

- The RESONATE project synergises well with the EU biodiversity policy, which is echoed in the [EU Forest Strategy for 2030](#); a cross-cutting plan of action to ensure forests as multifunctional and resilient ecosystems which can meet different societal, economic and environmental demands. Many of the findings in the policy brief also underpin the actions in the EU Forest Strategy and its key deliverables.
- From existing data and knowledge on forest biodiversity (mostly from [Natura 2000](#) sites), we can see that the status and trends for forest biodiversity is mixed. The way forests are managed has a major impact on their dynamics. Biodiversity contributes to forest resilience and efforts to improve biodiversity in forests feature strongly in different policy frameworks.
- The EU published in 2023 a [set of guidelines including Closer-To-Nature Forest Management and for Biodiversity-Friendly Afforestation and Reforestation](#). These align well with the recommendations in the RESONATE Policy Brief #2.
- Unfortunately, there is a perception that the [Nature Restoration Regulation \(NRR\)](#) is about looking towards the past. However, climate change adaptation looking forward into the future is in fact an important and integral component of the NRR.
- The role of critical enablers such as capacity building and support is important along with the concept of payment for ecosystem services (PES) to build a business case for biodiversity-positive forest management.
- Striking the right balance between different demands for forest ecosystem services and functions requires quantifiable or qualifiable parameters to set thresholds, benchmarks and targets that provide a knowledge base and facilitate a level playing field for forest industry and forest owners e.g. on actual needs for increasing deadwood volumes or structural complexity so as to have meaningful benefits for biodiversity.
- The EC is exploring the potential of nature credits and biodiversity certification schemes. In relation to forests, the EC has started to look at possible options for the closer-to-nature certification scheme to be included in the EU Forest Strategy for 2030.
- Knowledge on forest biodiversity standards and trends in European forests is fragmented and insufficient today.
- The EC has put forward a proposal for establishing an EU framework for a [Forest Monitoring Law](#) to reinforce and complement national monitoring efforts. The proposal is currently negotiated by the co-legislators.

2.3 DG Research and Innovation statement

Minna Huttunen, Seconded National Expert, Policy Officer, [European Commission Directorate-General Research and Innovation \(DG RTD\)](#)

Ph.D. in human nutrition, research at universities in Finland and the USA, work experience in advertising and the food industry. Since 2013, Ministerial Adviser at Finland’s Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. Joined the EC’s Bioeconomy and Food Systems Unit as a Seconded National Expert.

- Bioeconomy is a global topic and gaining increasing traction. Today more than 60 countries have a bioeconomy strategy. The European Commission’s international bioeconomy cooperation targets global initiatives such as the G20. Global partnerships such as the [International Bioeconomy Forum \(IBF\)](#) are also significant for research and innovation. The FAO is also preparing a multi-stakeholder [global bioeconomy initiative](#).
- RESONATE’s Policy Brief #3 contains valuable key recommendations. I’d like to add thoughts for policy development and research to complement these recommendations:
 - Public stakeholder engagement is important to advance value chain development. The policy brief highlights rightfully the social aspects, the inclusiveness and the socioeconomic resilience aspects.
 - Data needs: Comprehensive data is key for research and innovation, but we are not yet there. Main data needs are: i) biomass availability, ii) effectiveness of novel technology, and iii) whole value chain data needs.
 - Circularity: How can we integrate circularity into the use of alternative applications used and developed? How is circularity managed in logistics and the new tools we are developing?

Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

Key recommendations:	Additional thoughts for policy development & research
1. Raise awareness of the risk gap	1. Public stakeholder engagement , building fair value chain, best practice sharing
2. Increase knowledge and develop efficient technologies	2. Novel technologies for diverse biomass use, DATA
3. Safeguard socio-economic resilience	3. Policies to support social inclusiveness & socio-economic resilience
4. Develop harvesting technologies and logistics	4. Environmental & economic impact, circularity in strategies
5. Address tipping points in availability	5. Descale harmful activities, focus on high-value product development
6. Explore alternative species and applications	6. Sustainable circularity!
7. Prioritise forest ecosystem services	7. Public stakeholder engagement
8. Invest in long-term integrated resilience research	8. Value chain approach, DATA

Figure 3 Summary slide of feedback on key recommendations by DG RTD

2.4 DG Agriculture statement

Tamas Szedlak is Project Officer at [European Commission Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development \(DG AGRI\)](#).

He provided an overview of EC instruments to support resilience. In theory, all sorts of adaptation measures and interventions can be supported by the EU funds of the [Common Agricultural Policy \(CAP\)](#) or through national funds as state aid. A variety of different adaptation measures are eligible for support (see Figure 4):

- Afforestation, creation of new forests and wooded areas, introducing new species such as broadleaf species, enhancing existing forests
- Prevention and restoration measures
- Socio-economic aspects: changing the structure of the forests to improve the social functions and recreational value and/or economic value of the forest
- Nature: measures to boost biodiversity
- Increasing variety of income for landowners to mitigate rural exodus and land abandonment
- Compensation for Natura 2000 constraints or supporting voluntary forest conservation commitments, and preservation and propagation and genetic resources, to have appropriate varieties, species and provenances for restoration.

Public support instruments can only compensate for the real cost, so it is not an incentive. But under state aid, member states have a possibility to pay more for certain specific commitments, such as climate, biodiversity, water and soil.

CAP, State Aids and Resilience – DG AGRI

- Public supports for sustainable forest management cover sustainable resilience. There is no real sustainability without covering all aspects; economic, environmental and social.
- **CAP Rural Development Policy** – RD Programs, CAP Strategic Plans to implement actions needed to build on resilience. (RD 2013-2022 planned amounts, still ongoing implementation)
- Afforestation and agroforestry with consideration of climate change, biodiversity and bioeconomy (€2.0 bn and €27 m respectively)
- Managing disturbances, Prevention and restoration (€2.2 bn and €645 m)
- Increasing resilience and improving biodiversity and social value of existing forests (€1.4 bn)
- Increasing economic value and wood mobilisation, processing (€748 m)
- NATURA 2000 compensation (€ 300 m)
- Voluntary forest-environment commitments compensation, genetic resources (€345 m)
- **+ State aid**, beyond the above in case of specific commitments on climate, biodiversity, soil and water the support may go beyond the costs and income losses by 20% “~PES”

1

Figure 4 Summary slide on CAP support for forestry by DG AGRI

Note: This statement was given during the Group discussion 2 ‘Disturbances’.

2.5 DG GROW statement

Katarzyna Kwiecinska, Policy Officer, [European Commission Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs \(DG GROW\)](#)

- The forest-based bioeconomy accounts for around 20% of the added value that the overall bioeconomy is producing, which shows the significance of the sector.
- The industry is truly a 'made in Europe' industry, starting from sustainable sourcing through established bioeconomy chains with high innovation potential. It aligns fully with the new top priorities of the EU: competitiveness and decarbonisation. Forest-based industries have a role to play in 'defossilisation' potential; they offer high potential for creating added value in substitution of fossil materials and fuels.
- There are a number of policy synergies where the forest value chains can make the link to existing and announced new initiatives, including the [Life Sciences Strategy](#), the revised [Bioeconomy Strategy](#), the [Biotech Act](#), the [Circular Economy Act](#) and the [Industrial Decarbonisation Accelerator Act](#), among others.
- We strive for efficient use of the resource. The issue of underused hardwoods in the value chain is an important one. In future there will be much more hardwood species/availability in the EU. Today, unfortunately most of the hardwoods harvested are not valorised, contrary to softwoods.
- The key question is: How do we then establish resilient value chains based on hardwoods to utilise the resource more efficiently?
- Sustainable active forest management is the pre-condition. We see huge differences across the EU (e.g. the presented cases from the Czech Republic and from Spain). In some parts of Europe, there are abandoned, unmanaged forests. So a main focus must be: how can these resources be brought into active management ?

Note: This statement was given during the Group discussion 3 'Resilient value chains'.

3 Impulse talks by regional representatives and industry

3.1 Czech Ministry of Agriculture statement

Tomáš Krejzar, Director, [Department of Forest Policy and Economics, Czech Ministry of Agriculture](#).

He has a PhD in tree physiology, and long experience in forest-related international affairs, state aid, forest research and communication. He also has been serving as a bureau member of the [United Nations' Forum on Forests \(UNFF\)](#).

Overview of the large-scale disturbance events in Czech Republic (Figure 5)

- The normal level of felling/removals used to be about 15 million m³/year before the bark beetle outbreak. During the outbreak it more than doubled to 35.5 million m³. At the peak of calamity, 95% of all removals could be attributed to salvage felling. In the last years, about 40% were still salvage fellings caused by storms.
- Regarding forest regeneration, the situation has improved rather quickly due to favourable weather conditions and precipitation above average. However, in 2023 there were still about 54,000 hectares to be regenerated.
- In total 225,000 hectares of forest stands dominated by coniferous species have been affected by bark beetles. These are vast areas, but they still represent only 13.1% of all Czech forests. There remain a lot of spruce stands in Czech forests, which is positive from the perspective of industry, but represent also large risks.
- There have been two significant policy responses: a new [State Forest Policy until 2030](#) and a new [National Wood Policy](#) focusing on efficient use of wood resources have been developed. The policy goal is not to increase harvesting, but to use forest resources more effectively and to add more value domestically, rather than to export unprocessed roundwood.
- Legislative changes to the rules of regeneration and forest management planning are aiming to reduce bureaucratic burdens and simplify procedures for forest owners, allowing more flexibility and freedom also for adaptation measures, for example
 - The prolongation of time period for forest regeneration
 - We are considering to allow shorter rotation periods for spruce and the introduction of payments for ecosystem services.
 - Through an amendment of the game management act we try to strengthen the role of forest owners and state administration in game management to reduce the damage of trees by browsing in areas damaged by bark beetles.
- During the peak of the crisis, compensation payments were given as state aid to forest owners to partly compensate the loss caused by bark beetles. In the second stage, we supported the restoration of affected forest stands, financed from state budgets and the EU's recovery and resilience facility.

BARK BEETLE OUTBREAK AND ITS IMPACT ON CZECH FORESTS

Source: Czech Statistical Office/ Czech Forestry Institute

STRATEGIES APPLIED AND MEASURES TAKEN BY PUBLIC AUTHORITIES

Ultimate goal: to have resilient forests, well-adapted to climate change.

- ✓ New **State Forest Policy until 2030** + its strategic implementing document
- ✓ **National Wood Policy**
- ✓ **Amendments of Ministerial Decrees** (forest protection, forest regeneration, forest management planning)
- ✓ **Amendments of Forest Act**
 - Reduction/simplification of obligations for forest owners
 - More flexibility for adaptation measures (prolonged time limits for forest regeneration and forest establishment; shortened rotation period, etc.)
 - Introduction of payments for forest ecosystem services
- ✓ **Amendment of Game Management Act**
 - strengthening the role of forest owner and state administration in the management of game with a goal to reduce damage of trees by browsing, as a basic precondition to successful restoration of forests and their adaptation to climate change
- ✓ The **state aid to forest owners** was multiplied in the period of drought and bark beetle outbreak (overall CZK 26,2 bill., i.e. **EUR 1 bill.**, was provided in **2018-2023**).
- ✓ As part of it, **bark beetle compensation payments** for forest owners were introduced at the peak of the calamity to partially compensate owners and provide them with finances to keep caring for their forests and reforest the affected forest stands (CZK 12,9 bill., i.e. **EUR 516 mill.**).

Figure 5 Overview slides on bark beetle outbreaks and resilience measures in the Czech Republic

3.2 Catalonia Forest Owners statement

Teresa Baiges Zapater, [Centre de la Proprietat Forestal \(CPF\)](#), Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

Forest and agriculture engineer with a Master in agroforestry. She has worked in forestry research, knowledge-share and extension for over 15 years.

Overview of forestry and resilience in Catalonia, Spain

- In Catalonia, the most important issue is the underdeveloped active forest management. The forest cover is dense, and the growing stock has been increasing, mainly due to rural abandonment during the last century. Only less than 30% of the growth is harvested. Biomass is accumulating in the forest which can cause severe threats.
- Forestry is based upon natural regeneration and continuous cover forestry. Forests are mostly mixed, but all disturbances mentioned in Resonate are present here.
- The typical mixed forests represent a transition phase: some coniferous species such as Scots pine are dying from drought, which means that only broadleaved trees are surviving. With water being the main limiting factor, it would require high efforts to maintain conifers here. So basically, we are transitioning in the opposite direction, from diverse mixed forests to rather homogeneous forests with lesser species or only broadleaved species.
- Some remnant oak forests were retained in the landscape from long ago, which used to be pasture lands, with large old holm oaks providing lots of micro-habitats.
- The conifer plantations are more abundant, which need to be managed. We fully support Resonate's message that thinning is seen as an important tool for enhancing resilience of forests.
- We also promote the increase of larger volumes of deadwood in the forest, but with a careful eye on the dynamics, the disturbances, the history and the context.
- During salvage logging, we do not have problems of insufficient stock/supply. The main bottleneck is a lack of sufficient labour in forestry to harvest and deliver the wood for processing. Hard outdoor work is not popular, the machinery in use is artisanal and not modernised, because we neglected this sector for decades. We are starting to reinvest, but the machinery is not well adapted and there is a huge lack of training on skills for both harvesting and silviculture.
- Very important for us in the future will be to strengthen associations and cooperation among small private forest owners to work on the landscape scale. Social resilience, including strong local communities is key to be able to react on disturbances.
- More cooperation across sectors is also needed, including agriculture, grazing, and water management. Social acceptance is key if we want to promote new approaches like payments for ecosystem services or prescribed burning for fire prevention.

3.3 Papierholz Austria statement

Dietmar Hagauer, Project manager,
Papierholz Austria (PHA)

PHA is a major wood purchasing company owned by several modern pulp- and paper mills in Austria. PHA purchases a range of timber assortments from PEFC-certified forests and provides professional support for the organisation of harvesting and timber logistics.

PHA is a Resonate partner representing a key industrial player in the value chain.

Perspective on forest resilience and wood supply in the future

- Tree species composition and distribution in Europe will change in the long-term.
 - Spruce will most likely not be available in certain elevations in central Europe to the same extent and amount as today, which is an issue for the whole wood sector.
 - Possibly more spruce will grow in Scandinavia, whereas in Central-Europe hardwood species will be dominating.
 - Performing R&D on fibre qualities and fibre composition for underused tree species is needed, to be prepared for these future shifts.
- Building up more decentralised storage facilities and terminals will be crucial. The huge volumes following calamities such as large storms or bark beetle calamities cannot be taken over immediately, and logistics might run out of capacities. These buffer storages contribute to overcome these bottlenecks. Besides reducing road distances from the forest to the mill it also proves PHA a liable partner in the supply chain by supporting foresters to get out the bark beetle-infested timber from the forest.
- But to be able to handle these large volumes, infrastructure - especially in the rail sector – needs to be enhanced. More loading points are needed as the situation will not be managed by using trucks only, also because an increase of truck traffic is not seen positively in society.

4 Parallel group sessions

The following chapters summarise the workshop participants' main comments to the Policy Briefs' recommendations. Two discussion rounds were held per each group, moderated by the RESONATE team. In the discussion, the participants addressed the priorities, relevance and constraints for the recommendation from their point of view. Missing aspects, additional recommendations and future research needs were also addressed.

In the following texts, the stakeholder target groups (TG) and the recommendations (Rx.x) of the Policy Briefs are referenced in brackets.

4.1 Group 1 – Disturbances

4.1.1 Priorities, Relevance and Constraints

Figure 6 Impressions from workshop group 1

The participants assigned the highest priorities (Table 3) to the recommendations “Support forest owners in the realization of adaptation measures” (R2.1: 13 votes), “Consider short-term costs vs. long-term effects” (R1.1: 8 votes) and “Adopt proactive approaches in high-risk stands” (R1.4: 8 votes). Other recommendations such as “Implement effective browsing control” (R1.5: 5 votes) and “Develop best practices in adaptive management” (R1.6: 6 votes) were also given attention. These recommendations under 1. and 2. were especially highlighted by the target groups European Commission (TG1), public (TG2) and private forest owners (TG3). The forest-based industries and value chain actors (TG4) put a special emphasis on the recommendation “Mainstream newly available information” (R3.2: 4 votes).

All these topics were reflected in the discussion, where participants elaborated on their preferences and provided additional feedback, as summarised in the following.

Table 3 Policy Brief #1 recommendations prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups					Observers	Count sum
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups		
<i>1.</i>	<i>Adapt forest management to disturbances</i>	9	6	7	4	2	1	29
1.1	Consider short-term costs vs. long-term effects	3	2		2	1		8
1.2	Actively exploit disturbed patches	1		1				2
1.3	Incorporate post-disturbance forest structures							0
1.4	Adopt proactive approaches in high-risk stands	4	2	2				8
1.5	Implement effective browsing control		1	3	1			5
1.6	Develop best practices in adaptive management	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
<i>2.</i>	<i>Adapt regulations and infrastructure</i>	6	3	7	3	2	0	21
2.1	Support forest owners in adaptation measures	3	3	4	1	2		13
2.2	Remove the salvage requirement	2						2
2.3	Enable adaptation to climate change			2				2
2.5	Safeguard nursery capacities	1		1				2
2.5	Support the establishment of storage				2			2
<i>3.</i>	<i>Improve data and planning</i>	1	0	0	4	0	3	8
3.1	Forest restoration requires						1	1
3.2	Mainstream newly available information	1			4		1	6
3.3	Use emerging remote sensing						1	1
	Sum	16	9	14	11	4	4	58

Note: Each participant was asked to choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important. The counts per group of recommendations (headings in italics) are sums calculated based on the votes per recommendation.

Proactive approaches in high risk stands (R1.4), salvage requirements (R2.2), and exploit disturbed patches (R1.2)

- National regulations often represent major barriers to work effectively with natural regeneration and effective restoration measures.
- Czech Republic: Prolonging forest recovery period has proven useful for state aid financing and gave more flexibility. But both early and late regeneration measures are being financed.
- Flexible/right recovery time window for restoration should be adapted to local site conditions (climate, soil, flora, fauna). Risk that longer heat waves can impact on soils and foster spread of grass species. Acting fast is useful to protect microclimate.
- Limited availability of seeds and nursery material is a critical problem across EU. Should be addressed in national forest regeneration programmes.
- Disturbance areas: being pragmatic, take practical steps to start the transition to other tree species and change mindset of forest owners
- Pests and diseases: not only about bark beetles

Support owners, financial support, competence building (R2.1)

- Resilience silviculture generally cost more. Money becomes available after large disasters for immediate action, but this is only reacting to the problem. Once the crisis fades away, also the financial aid is diminishing.
- There is a large lack of sufficient funding to act and implement these adaptation measures and new management systems.
- There is a lack of funds to take preventive action and take on ambitious large-scale restoration efforts. Effective incentive systems also for ecosystem services are needed.

- Focus should not just be on incentives/funding, but also be on continuous, more structural support and soft measures for forest owners, including forest extension services, education, training and guidelines to enhance knowledge to build up capacity of forest owners in the long term.
- Especially also forest professionals advising landowners must gain a good practical knowledge about forest adaptation to choose and implement measures in the right way. Private owners need to gain trust to implement it.
- Raise awareness for lesser-known topics, like soil restoration or assisted migration
- Available/declining workforce in forestry is widespread issue. Especially a lack of skilled forest workers who are confident with complex silviculture

Mainstream data / Landscape-level planning tools for risk and resilience (R3.2)

- Very important to address climate change issue appropriately. Mainstreaming of data, prioritisation of measures, and proper planning will be key.
- Not just “mainstreaming” available information, but build up a dedicated spatially explicit forestry risk assessment as basis for decision-making
- We also lack a real economic evaluation which risks can have which potential impact in the long term, and where should be the focus: high risk or low risk areas? What does it mean for economic viability of forest management?
- Integrate biodiversity restoration and forest connectivity on landscape level, rather than silo approaches.
- Issue for building data portals and DSS: many forest owners and other actors in the value chain are reluctant to give access to data, for various reasons.

Browsing control (R1.5)

- Major factor across Europe reducing management efforts, big threat for climate adaptation and biodiversity
- Hot topic with many very conflictual views, need new approaches

Nature restoration, Natura2000 areas (R2.3)

- Biodiversity measures and converting forests into protected areas: knowledge transfer and advice to owners how to do it right is key.
- Natura 2000 guidance exists, EC has done their homework. Gap to implementation is that regional and local administrations may be informed, but it does not reach well the practitioners on the ground.
- Practitioners often are reluctant to adopt when it is seen as top-down guidelines from Brussels, so taking in account the point of view of forest owners is also important.
- Conflicting goals/measures proposed from different responsible public administrations are not helpful in the field.
- Increasing number of tree species is not enough regarding diversity. Structural diversity of forests must also be addressed.

General comments how to structure and to prioritise the recommendations

- Useful to point out which target group is addressed or even to group them per target group (forest owners/managers, policy makers, etc).
- Another suggested order of recommendations: i) Resilience of forests, ii) Raising interests of forest owners and managers, iii) Improve knowledge base and decision support tools.

- Focus on feasibility for implementation: ideal solutions or scenarios often are not realistic in the real world, or fall short to take into account the economic and social realities (good example for local complexity: browsing control)

4.1.2 Research Needs

The participants discussed and highlighted various important topics for future research:

- Tree species selection and forest adaptation management systems to deal with risks and climate change: which species/system for which local site.
- Economic evaluation/impact assessment of resilience adaptation: What are the extended costs (including economic losses) for public and private owners and managers for implementing the different proposed resilience measures, what does it mean in different regions?
- Wood products and industry research: How to adapt to changes in wood supply and assortments, what to do with underused and less favoured tree species/hardwoods, how to create valuable products? In the near future through innovation, wood industries will most likely be able to use all sorts of wood resources. Transport costs will be a critical factor.
- Research into constraints and social dynamics, also looking at relationship between conservation goals, productivity and resilience. Socio-economic resilience is not yet well understood.
- Implementation gap: Knowledge needs to reach practitioners, best practices in some regions need to be shared better. And what are the real reasons behind why forest owners refrain from forest adaptation and conversion? Many complex limitations and barriers need to be better understood. Big challenge is that we are dealing with uncertain long-term future, so the decision what to plant is not trivial.
- Land abandonment: More and more forest owners stop to actively manage their forests. This is already a major factor in Southern Europe, will become an even more severe problem with growing disturbances. Strategies and solutions are urgently needed.
- Browsing control: science-based groundwork needed to address this highly conflictual topic, develop new/more effective ways of deer management
- Pests: self-adaptation capacity of tree species
- Natura2000 sites: what are the best adapted tree species

4.2 Group 2 – Biodiversity

4.2.1 Priorities, Relevance and Constraints

Figure 7 Impressions from workshop group 2

The participants assigned the highest priorities (Table 4) to the recommendations “Support forests with tree species mixture” (4.1.1: 10 votes), “Develop training programmes” (4.3.1: 8 votes) and “Tailor your management to local needs” (5.3.1: 9 votes). In addition, other recommendations such as “Foster natural regeneration” (4.2.1: 4 votes), “Offer subsidies or payments” (4.3.2: 4 votes) and “Balance biodiversity and timber production” (5.1.2: 4 votes) were also given attention. There was a fairly common agreement of these priorities across the stakeholder groups.

These topics dominated the discussion, and participants elaborated on their preferences and gave additional feedback, which are summarised in the following.

Tree species mixture with functional diversity (R4.1.1)

- Top priority topic, it is the way to go for higher resilience.

Deer management to reduce browsing (R4.1.2)

- Major priority issue that prevents natural regeneration into more species-diverse forests. Lots of invested work and funding is being lost through browsing.

Foster natural regeneration (R4.2.1)

- Key measure, more biodiversity will help building resilient forests. But it is not always the better choice: in many forests natural regeneration is spruce again.

Deadwood retention (R4.2.3)

- Useful for biodiversity itself, but also as a resilience measure: deadwood as habitat for natural predators that can keep harmful insect populations low

Table 4 Policy Brief #2 recommendations prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups						Count sum
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups	Observers	
	Number of participants per target group	10	2	5	5	3	3	28
4.	For Policymakers	7	2	4	1	2	3	19
4.1	<i>Promote tree diversity</i>	3	2	3	0	1	1	10
4.1.1	Support forests with tree species mixture	3	1	1		1	1	7
4.1.2	Foster the management of deer population		1	2				3
4.2	<i>Promote forest management structural diversity</i>	4	0	1	1	1	2	9
4.2.1	Foster natural regeneration	2				1	1	4
4.2.2	Advance uneven-aged forests	1		1				2
4.2.3	Promote deadwood retention	1			1		1	3
4.3	<i>Provide financial and training support for forest m.</i>	3	2	2	0	4	1	12
4.3.1	Develop training programs	2	1	2		2	1	8
4.3.2	Offer subsidies or payments	1	1			2		4
5.	For Forest Owners and Managers	5	1	5	2	3	1	17
5.1	<i>Support ecosystem and economic resilience</i>	1	1	3	1	0	0	6
5.1.1	Diversify free species			2				2
5.1.2	Balance biodiversity and timber production	1	1	1	1			4
5.2	<i>Use disturbances to spark biodiversity</i>	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
5.2.1	Retain natural features							0
5.2.2	Mimic disturbances				1			1
5.3	<i>Diversify your measures</i>	4	0	2	0	3	1	10
5.3.1	Tailor your management to local needs	3		2		3	1	9
5.3.2	Set small forest patches aside							0
5.3.3	Manage browsing efficiently							0
5.3.4	Foster natural regeneration	1						1
	Sum	12	3	9	3	5	4	36

Note: Each participant was asked to choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important. The counts per group of recommendations (headings in italics) are sums calculated based on the votes per recommendation.

Training programs (R4.3.1)

- Training is a major need. It is usually not the first priority for small forest owners.
- Raising awareness and providing knowledge about biodiversity benefits and how to manage biodiversity in the right way (use of natural regeneration, habitat trees, etc).
- Practical down-to-earth measures needed so that owners can adopt them easily.
- Good communication, narratives: owners need to believe in it and feel proud.
- Large regional differences: well established training systems in highly productive EU countries, underdeveloped or missing in other countries.
- Very specialised skills needed for forest work in mountainous and/or Mediterranean regions, regarding the terrain but also the biodiversity.
- Train forest owners also on their responsibilities regarding risks, to properly manage forests so that forest fires don't get out of control.
- Resilience and biodiversity topics need also be included in university education/curricula for the next generation of foresters.

Subsidies or payments (R4.3.2)

- Required to most proposed adaptation and restoration measures, because resilience and biodiversity will make harvesting more costly > difficult to mobilise owners
- Incentives of best practices for holistic management. need to adjust them for biodiversity
- Public officers and private professionals dealing with subsidies need proper training about resilience and biodiversity, to manage funds correctly in a meaningful way.

Balance diversity and timber production (R5.1.2)

- Public forests: responsibility for conservation of forests is often placed on public owners, but many municipalities and public estates depend on income from timber production: need for balanced approaches.
- Payments for ecosystem services (PES) as a possible business model. Spanish example: harvesting companies create micro-habitats as part of timber extraction operations, mimicking disturbances.

Tailor management to local needs (R5.3.1)

- Forest managers: very important to adjust any proposed solutions to the local context, plenty of locally suitable measures needed.
- Policy-makers: “one-size-fits-all” policies are not feasible. EU policies must be general and cannot cover all details, but the varieties and differences of forests, ownership, regulations, etc. across Europe make local solutions and local policy development or interpretation a necessity.
- Also on regional level: Central-European views dominate in policy, but Mediterranean or Eastern countries might have a very different perspective and needs.
- Challenging because regional/local specific policies/approaches can also come into conflict with other strategies (e.g. biodiversity not aligned with bioeconomy strategy)

More recommendations, what’s missing

- “Climate-adapted species”: the term is not highlighted sufficiently in the Resonate recommendations, yet it is the more useful term to link the tree species discussion to the big picture of climate change. “Native” or “local” species (hard to define what is native) or “natural regeneration” are not the best approaches. Climate change is altering the suitable range of species, assisted migration might become very important.
- Biodiversity is integral for resilience and also productivity: it must be highlighted much more. It is not just about tree species, but about all biodiversity, and many other aspects (soil, fungi, etc) are much overlooked. Soils are so important for forest management, but people/owners are not aware, they lack to understand the whole picture.

4.2.2 Research Needs

The participants discussed and highlighted various important topics for future research:

Biodiversity, impacts/benefits of adaptation of forests, monitoring

- Benefits of biodiversity: How can various other species or species communities be used to enhance resilience (predators of pests, improving soils, etc)? Which are the best areas to promote biodiversity?
- Flexible frameworks and meaningful, quantifiable indicators for local level: Indicators for forest management approaches such as continuous cover forestry (CCF), close to nature forestry (CNF), reduced impact logging, etc. need to be further developed and operationalized. Deadwood volume or number retention trees in forests is much lower than a minimum to sustain many endangered species. Indicators would give forest owners a reference to know how much effort is needed to achieve a certain goal, and could be ranked according to the level of ambition. The available knowledge is vague, and debates are often on an ideological level. Outcome-based indicators are needed that are useful for forest managers and can be harnessed for policy goals.
- Build on existing schemes: don't develop new certification schemes. It took 30 years to develop existing schemes (FSC, PEFC), and today only 10% of the world's forests are certified. Voluntary schemes have not been very effective.
- Measurements: new tech/sensors can be exploited. Need to carefully balance the huge amount of data required versus the real gain.
- Regeneration monitoring: How to do it effectively, can it be done with remote sensing? What can be predicted regarding species diversity and growth?

Financial aspects/opportunities of biodiversity

- How to make biodiversity attractive to foresters and landowners? Can benefits be a tool to promote biodiversity? How should specific incentives for biodiversity be designed? Should financial incentives follow an input approach (paid before intervention) or output approach (paid after intervention)?
- What are the real costs? Better understanding of economic versus environmental balance, especially for rural communities. Look deeper into regional cases where higher biodiversity also has led to stable or higher economic returns.
- Valuation of biodiversity outcomes: What are costs and benefits? Which are the right instruments? Payment for ecosystem services (PES), subsidies from state/regional authorities, or others? Natural capital accounting is the right method. There are still inconsistencies between countries, but standardization of frameworks is ongoing.

Specific topics

- Protection versus production: The Biodiversity strategy talks a lot about protection, but Resonate recommends mainly integration/balanced management. Clarification of concepts and common language needed, what are the biodiversity objectives exactly?
- New pests and disease risks: Don't focus only on bark beetle, there are many other pests affecting tree species. How to prepare for new threats? We have very little research on prevention.
- DNA-based tree species identification tool: need for law enforcement in international timber trade. Aim to have a credible test in 20 min if it is a strictly protected tree species.
- Public opinion on biodiversity: What does the public want for "their" public forests?

4.3 Group 3 – Value chains

4.3.1 Priorities, Relevance and Constraints

Figure 8 Impressions from workshop group 3

Table 5 Policy Brief #3 recommendations prioritised by workshop participants

No.	Recommendation	Stakeholder target groups					Count sum	
		European Commission	Public forest owners + state bodies	Private forest owners + advisory bodies	Forest-based industries + value chain	NGOs and interest groups		Observers
	Number of workshop participants per target group	10	2	5	5	3	3	28
6.	Raise awareness of the risk gap	2		3	1			6
7.	Increase knowledge on forest adaptation		1		3			4
8.	Develop measures to safeguard socio-economic	1		2		1		4
9.	Develop flexible, efficient harvesting	1	1		2			4
10.	Acknowledge the growing risk of tipping points							0
11.*	Explore alternative species	2		2	1			5
11.1	Diversification and resource efficiency	2						2
11.2	Innovation towards higher value-added		1	1	1			3
11.3	Promote the cascading principle and a circular	4			1			5
12.	Prioritise forest ecosystem services	1						1
13.	Invest in long-term, integrated resilience	3		1	2	1		7

Note: Each participant was asked to choose up to three recommendations that he/she considered as most important.

* Some participants voted for the whole group, others voted for the sub-recommendations.

The participants prioritised the value chain related policy recommendations as follows (Table 5). The recommendations group 11 “Explore alternative species” received the highest ranking (in total 15 votes; 5 participants highlighted the whole group, while 7 other participants highlighted the specific sub-recommendations). Secondly, the recommendations “Raise awareness of the risk gap” (R6: 6 votes) and “Invest in long-term integrated resilience research” (R13: 7 votes) received also significant attention. Furthermore, the recommendations (R7 – R10: each 4 votes) were considered as relevant.

The highlighted priorities are quite spread across the stakeholder groups, showing a fair agreement among participants. A notable emphasis was given by the European policy makers (TG1) to the recommendation “Promote the cascading principle and a circular economy” (R11.3: 4 votes).

All these topics dominated the discussion, and participants elaborated on their preferences and gave additional feedback, which are summarised in the following.

Raising awareness about risk gap, partnerships and cooperatives (R6)

- Joint advocacy of forest owners/managers and wood industry: in Austria and Germany, the national associations representing both groups hold regular meetings to define joint decisions and positions regarding upcoming policies. To find an agreement, you have to find a common interest or incentive for both sides. Besides these groups, you also need to raise awareness among all the other stakeholder groups.
- Encourage active forest management by means of creating a closer link between forestry and wood industry. Value chain is dependent on wood supply and needs to adapt in the long run to change of species composition.
- New collaborative business models are needed: In Sweden or Finland exist large cooperatives of forest owners and industries, but they are missing in the rest of Europe. This lack of vertical integration is a major weakness. We need to move from cooperation to real collaboration and integration, which means joining businesses and creating new businesses models.
- Other forest products also need collaborative models: In Southern Europe, supplies of main products such as cork, resin or poplar have declined. Therefore, new collaborative organisations have been founded (e.g., Pro-Populus in Italy or Centro Pinus in Portugal) to secure the supply of resources and facilitate the marketing of products.
- Small ownership structure is a main challenge: The large number of private owners (including urban forest owners), small size of forest parcels and high number of local forest management associations or producer groups (e.g. several hundred in Bavaria) are a major barrier. This represents an unequal partnership with wood industries, which is a constraint for more collaboration. Forest owners need to self-organize better and professionalize their activities.
- Funding through CAP? The amount of funding for forestry has been reduced by half, because the Member States set a higher priority for agriculture. We can learn from the examples how agricultural value chains with small producers (milk, wine, etc) have changed over the past.
- Best practices of cooperatives must be shared more broadly in Europe, because forest ownership structures are very different across Europe. Example Aquitaine in France: 30 years ago they had 100 cooperatives, today there is only one “Alliance Foret-Bois” which now sells 5 million cubic meters.

Socio-economic resilience (R8)

- Point is closely linked to the need to establish/strengthen cooperatives, so both recommendations could be merged.

Explore alternative species, new applications, hardwoods (R11)

- Policy Brief #3 is lacking a clear link to biodiversity: How will industry deal with changing sourcing patterns related to more biodiversity-friendly forest management practices (CCF, close-to-nature forestry, more individual tree selection, etc)? The supply will become much more heterogeneous, you will not obtain a certain type/assortment of timber in a constant manner. Processing facilities need to become flexible to handle the variability of the future timber supply.
- Hardwoods and softwoods are two completely different material groups: You need entirely different processing machinery in sawmills, which is bulky, costly equipment with long-term investments. Also the produced products are different, and relate to very different specialised markets. So the practical realisation of this transition will be extremely challenging for sawmills and other wood industries.
- Consumer and market perspective needs to be included: While the forest is changing more and more to the provision of hardwoods, the market demand driven by society is turning more to softwoods (e.g. shorter lifetime of furniture). All international studies point to an increase of demand for softwoods (solid wood products, but not only), while the demand for hardwoods remains rather low, compared to the potential supply. It is also a matter of prices: hardwoods harvesting, transportation and processing is more costly. Europe is not an island and wood products are a global commodity, with major softwood supplier markets nearby (Russia, North America, South America), so it will not be easy to be competitive. We must be careful not to end up in a situation where we penalize our local wood industry.

Invest into long-term, integrated resilience research (R13)

- This recommendation received the single highest priority from participants (7 votes). The relevant feedback and discussions are summarised in the following subchapter.

4.3.2 Research needs

The participants discussed and highlighted various important topics for future research.

A systemic, sectoral approach to the hardwoods question

- How to address the paradoxical situation of diminishing softwoods and large underused resources of hardwoods with almost no market? Today 60-80% of hardwoods are used directly as fuelwood and bioenergy, or are exported as raw timber to other countries, and we expect to have even more hardwoods in our future forests. This is a key question for the entire forest-based sector!
- A broader narrative and ambition for forests and industry is needed: The forest-based bioeconomy is a true domestic industry with a high innovation potential, that relies on sustainable forest management as precondition and can deliver on decarbonization and substitution. It is fully in line with the EU priorities, but we must connect it better to the new industrial policies and the competitiveness narrative from a systemic perspective.
- Dialogue between forest owners and industry needs to be strengthened to find a common ground between both sides, because both depend on each other. A difficulty is that industry plans usually some 10 to 15 years ahead but not longer, whereas forestry takes a much longer time horizon in perspective. Industries are also reluctant to change anything as long as softwood supplies in their region are still abundant.

Innovative hardwoods technologies can drive a shift to more resilient value chains

- R&I on more efficient and new harvesting and processing technology is needed for hardwoods: Hardwoods are heavier, so you need new equipment such as trailers, skidders, trucks and adapted sawmill equipment. Modern harvesters are designed for softwoods but cannot deal with hardwoods which grow not straight and have much more branches. New harvesting systems must also be cost-efficient to deal with smaller volumes and at the same time ensure low environmental impacts.
- New uses and value chains might offer the solution: Softwoods have a large gain for high value solid timber, but hardwoods are a much more heterogeneous resource (e.g., more branches and bark, higher variability of wood qualities). Novel uses such as biochar, bioplastics, textiles or biorefinery products are possible feasible opportunities, but they are mostly still under development and are not yet sufficiently competitive to be scaled up. A major investment into a hardwoods biorefinery is UPM in Leuna, Germany. More support for R&I and demonstration is needed, e.g. under the CBE-JU programme.
- Research with industry is key to unleash disruptive innovation in solid wood products from hardwoods: Example of the Weizer Group in Austria, a major parquet producer which invests into novel high-tech uses of hardwood appliances for trains (for the next ICE generation). Hardwoods is one of the strongest materials, and they managed to reach the performance needed for trains. Today they are also building a large incubator (Wood Vision Lab) for startups to bring basic research until the market (from TRL 1 to 9) in one place together.
- Cascading principle, resource efficiency, circular use: We must address the question what the sustainable limits of multifunctional forest supply are, given the growing demand for many new uses, and that we do not externalise problems by increasing imports to Europe on a large scale. People overestimate the supply capacity of forests. Resource efficiency must be the main goal, to optimise the consumption according to the cascading principle, and to develop also circular uses of wood. Wood construction is booming, and you can already find innovations such as design-for-disassembly solutions (e.g. new joints and connectors, built-in sensors), but the main engineered wood products used (CLT, GLT) are not per se circular. So this must be a main priority for research, because it is a very complex challenging topic.

A long-term horizon for research and capacity building

- Long-term R&I with public support: However, now is exactly the right moment to start more collaborative R&I, so that we can break open these tricky questions in a disruptive way, before it becomes a real supply issue for the wood industry. The topic of value chain resilience is not yet on the radar of decision-makers and funding organisations. There is a need to understand the interactions, risks and synergies in value chains, and how resilience adaptation and innovation can support the transformation.
- Education and training of forest managers and forest workers will also be key: the future forest management will require better trained, skilled managers and workers, to make the right decisions about the use of trees and reduce the impacts of harvesting on the ecosystem. The forest work must be better recognised to attract more workforce, so that we can ensure that we have the capacities for good forest management.

5 Conclusions

The RESONATE project has delivered a broad basis of research findings on forest resilience concepts, trends, case studies and proposed solutions, which are of high relevance to practitioners and decision-makers. The project has published three policy briefs addressing recommendations how to better manage disturbances, biodiversity and value chain resilience. The final policy workshop in Brussels brought together researchers with experts of the European Commission, public and private forest owners, industries, NGOs and other interest groups. The participants discussed the policy briefs in separate groups. Their dialogue provided valuable feedback regarding the relevance and level of priority, strengthening important aspects and further research needs. The main conclusions include:

- The EC policy officers confirmed that the research results are well aligned with many ongoing and upcoming policy initiatives of the different involved DGs, highlighting key aspects of relevance for the EC.
- Climate change is a long-term challenge affecting both forest ecosystems and forest-based value chains. Enhancing forest resilience is a complex goal, and the proposed solutions for adapting forests to increasing disturbances and ecosystemic shifts must therefore address the issues in a holistic, systemic manner.
- The discussions highlighted that solutions must be well balanced in view of stakeholder needs. Markets and consumers are main drivers and represent dominant interests, but equally important dimensions are the protection of ecosystem functions, biodiversity and social benefits of forest resilience, which need special attention. It is therefore necessary to negotiate trade-offs between economic and ecological goals, considering the interests of involved actors. Any meaningful solution must factor in the specific local and regional contexts of forestry in Europe and aim for the best, balanced outcome.
- The challenge is to achieve an integrated value chain approach that can build on science-based, validated methods and transferable measures. It entails widespread awareness raising, knowledge sharing, cooperation support and joint action of actors on all levels. Wider adoption and mainstreaming of forest resilience solutions among policy makers and practitioners across the EU will require a commitment of key public and private actors with appropriate financing for the implementation, including infrastructure development, capacity building (education/ training), and further research and innovation support.

6 References

RESONATE CORDIS project website, results section. <https://doi.org/10.3030/101000574>

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7 Annex

7.1 List of participating organisations

No	Organisation	Attendance
-	RESONATE research team / workshop facilitators	# persons
1	EFI European Forest Institute	4
2	InnovaWood	2
3	Prospex Institute	3
4	BOKU University	1
5	CZU Czech University of Life Sciences Prague	1
6	University of Helsinki	1
7	Bournemouth University	1
A	European Commission	
8	European Commission, DG RTD	2
9	European Commission, DG AGRI	2
10	European Commission, DG ENV	2
11	European Commission, DG CLIMA	1
12	European Commission, DG GROW	2
13	European Commission, EC REA	1
B	Public forest owners and state bodies	
14	MZE Ministry of Agriculture Czech Republic	1
15	EUSTAFOR	1
16	Forestry England	1
C	Private forest owners and advisory bodies	
17	CPF Centre de la Proprietat Forestal	1
18	CEPF Confederation of European Forest Owners	2
19	SRFB Société Royale Forestière de Belgique	1
20	LWF Bavarian State Institute of Forestry	1
21	CESEFOR	1
D	Forest-based industries and value chain actors	
22	Papierholz Austria	1
23	EOS European Organisation of the Sawmill Industries / CEI-Bois	1
24	UPM United Paper Mills	1
25	FBW Filière Bois Wallonie	1
26	Holzcluster Steiermark (Wood Cluster Styria)	1
E	Non governmental organisations and interest groups	
27	IUCN International Union for Conservation of Nature	1
28	Euromontana	1
29	FSC Forest Stewardship Council	1
-	Other: Observers	
30	Dendron Soluciones	1
31	IFSA SAN	1

7.2 Workshop agenda

Table 6 Agenda of the RESONATE policy workshop on 10 February 2025 in Brussels

Time	Session & Speakers
12:00	Arrival of participants, light lunch
13:00	Welcome, introduction to workshop, practicalities Gesche Schifferdecker, European Forest Institute (EFI)
13:10	RESONATE: Summary of key research findings and introduction to draft policy briefs Marcus Lindner, EFI Uwe Kies, Innovawood (IW) Dietmar Hagauer, Papierholz Austria
13:40	Impulse talks EU policy perspectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peter Loeffler, DG CLIMA: Resilience and climate change adaptation • Stefanie Schmidt, DG ENV: Resilience and Biodiversity • Minna Huttunen, DG RTD: Resilience and Bioeconomy Regional perspectives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomáš Krejzar, Czech Ministry of Agriculture: Input from Central/Northern Europe • Teresa Baiges Zapater, Centre De La Propietat Forestal (CPF), Forestry Administration of Catalunya, Spain
14:00	Introduction to Workshop and break-out groups Uwe Kies, IW & Nina Horstmann, Prospex Institute
14:10	Parallel group discussions, with brief contributions by Tamas Szedlak, DG AGRI : EC instruments to support resilience, and Katarzyna Kwiecińska, DG GROW : forest value chains role for the bioeconomy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topic 1. Resilience to disturbances and climate change adaptation. • Topic 2. Resilience and biodiversity • Topic 3. Value chain resilience
15:25	Coffee break
15:55	Summary of Workshop results and discussion - Plenary
16:35	Final conclusions of workshop Marcus Lindner, EFI
16:45	Closing of workshop

7.3 RESONATE project summary presentation

Resilient forest value chains – enhancing resilience through natural and socio-economic responses

RESONATE: Summary of key research findings and introduction to policy briefs

Marcus Lindner (European Forest Institute),
Uwe Kies (InnovaWood) & **Dietmar Hagauer** (Papierholz Austria)

Rooting for Resilience: Policy workshop
Brussels, 10th February 2025

Horizon 2020 RIA, project no. 101000574
(April 2021 – March 2025)

10/02/2025
www.resonateforest.org
Policy Workshop

RESONATE aims to generate the needed knowledge and practices for making European forests, the services they provide, and related economic activities more resilient to future climate change and disturbances.

The diagram illustrates the 'Wood value chain' as a circular process. It starts with 'FOREST MANAGEMENT' (including carbon storage, non-wood products, and timber production) leading to 'PRIMARY PRODUCTS' (wooden logs). These are then transported to 'Processing' (factories), which produces 'SECONDARY PRODUCTS' (chairs, tables). These secondary products go through 'Consumption' and 'Trade/Export'. A 'Recycling' loop connects consumption back to primary products. A 'Thermal power plant' is also shown as a destination for wood products.

RESONATE: Resilient forest value chains – enhancing resilience through natural and socio-economic responses. Horizon 2020. Project no. 101000574, April 2021 – March 2025.

10/02/2025
www.resonateforest.org
Policy Workshop

Disturbance hotspots and increasing future risks

- Improved evidence about disturbances in European forests (Patacca et al. 2023)
- Disturbance hotspots identified from remote sensing, recognizing natural and human disturbances and their interlinkages (Seidl & Senf 2024)
- Risks are increasing, especially for bark beetles and other biotic risks (Patacca et al. 2023) and for wildfire (Grünig et al. 2023)

Probability of maximum fire sizes exceeding 2500 ha for future climate conditions (Grünig et al. 2023).

nature communications

Changes in planned and unplanned canopy openings are linked in Europe's forests

Received: 2 October 2023

Report Status: & Corinna Senf

Accepted: 23 May 2024

Patacca et al. 2023. Policy Brief 4, European Forest Institute, <https://doi.org/10.36333/pb4>

10/02/2025

www.resonateforest.org

Operational Resilience Framework (ORF)

Lloret et al., 2024. Sustainability Science, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-024-01518-1>

Sustainability Science
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-024-01518-1>

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

ORF, an operational framework to measure resilience in social–ecological systems: the forest case study

Francisco Lloret^{1,2} · Pilar Hurtado^{2,3,4} · Josep Maria Espelta² · Luciana Jaime^{2,5} · Laura Nikinmaa^{6,7} · Marcus Lindner⁶ · Jordi Martínez-Vilalta^{1,2}

Forest modelling in 9 case studies across Europe

Forest model simulations from 1986-2020 with disturbances quantified from remote sensing data

- Resilience measure: **recovery of above ground biomass**
 - All case studies (except Galicia) were **resilient** when considering the entire forest **BUT!**
 - In areas affected by disturbances – majority of case studies were not resilient

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We need to **enhance resilience** in both forest management and forest value chains

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Silvicultural adaptation options (Willig and Bauhus 2024. RESONATE Deliverable 2.9)				
Reducing stand density (Thinning)	Shortening production times	Enhancing and maintaining tree species diversity (Mixing)	Introduction of more drought-tolerant species	Cessation of management
+ Resource availability + Initiating regeneration or transformation	+ Reducing disturbance risk	+ Diversification of risks + Beneficial species interactions	+ Transforming forests towards a more resilient stands	+ Forests adapt themselves through inherent self-regulating capacity
- Increased exposure to irradiance and wind	- Loss of old trees (biodiversity/recreation)	- More complicated tending and harvest operations	- Few experience with new species - Risk of maladaptation or invasiveness of new species	- Adaptive capacity do not match the pace of climate change (active management required)
Millar et al. (2007), Sohn et al. (2016), Spittlehouse and Stewart (2003), Steckel et al. (2020)	Gardiner and Quine (2000), Roberge et al. (2016)	Grossiord (2020), Jactel et al. (2017), Messier et al. (2021)	Aitken et al. (2008), Pötzelsberger et al. (2020), Royo et al. (2023)	Jandl et al. (2019), Lindner et al. (2020), Millar and Stephenson (2015), Puettmann (2011), Seidl et al. (2016)

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Biodiversity effect on forest resilience

- Forest storm resilience depends on the interplay between biodiversity and climate
 - Species-rich assemblages had higher recovery and resilience to storm disturbance
 - Functional diversity improved resistance and recovery
- Diverse forests with important share of slow-growing species promote higher resilience

Barrere et al. 2024. Functional Ecology 38, 500-516.

Received: 19 July 2023 | Accepted: 25 November 2023
 DOI: 10.1111/1365-2435.14489

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Functional Ecology

Forest storm resilience depends on the interplay between functional composition and climate—Insights from European-scale simulations

Julien Barrere | Björn Reineking | Maxime Jaunatre | Georges Kunstler

<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.14489>

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Resilient Forest Value Chains under changing conditions - 9 innovation pathways

- More innovation pathways for forest management than for the processing industries
- Diversification in forest management vs. efficiency in processing industry
- Leads to potential trade-offs

▲	Strengthens value chain resilience
▲	Strengthens forest resilience
▲	Evidence is mixed
D	Innovations that stimulate diversification
E	Innovations that stimulate efficiency
F	Innovations that stimulate flexibility

Hoeben, A. D., Stern, T., & Lloret, F. (2023). **A Review of Potential Innovation Pathways to Enhance Resilience in Wood-Based Value Chains.** *Current Forestry Reports*, 9(5), 301-318.

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Wood resource supply affects forest value chain resilience

- Overall, industry capacity aligns well with wood resources in three European countries
- Regionally, there is some undersupply of softwood
- Hardwood supply is larger than demand

Utilization of wood resources (EFISCEN-Space) vs. industry capacities (European Forest Industry Facilities Database).

Bozzolan et al. 2024. *Forest Policy and Economics* 169, 103358, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2024.103358>

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How flexible is societal demand under fast-changing circumstances?

Assessment of demand resilience in 8 RESONATE case studies (qualitative data from an expert survey):

- **Forest recreation and carbon sequestration** appear to be the **most resilient** ecosystem services.
- **Timber production and non-wood forest products** are assessed to be resilient due to the number and quality of **substitutes**.
- Cultural and regulating services (e.g. **ground water protection, soil erosion and avalanches**) are the **least resilient**

Lautrup et al., 2024. RESONATE - Deliverable 4.6.

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Introducing the RESONATE Policy Briefs

- Policy Brief #1 - Managing forest disturbances in a changing climate
<https://doi.org/10.36333/rs9>
- Policy Brief #2 - The role of biodiversity in making forests resilient
<https://doi.org/10.36333/rs7>
- Policy Brief #3 - Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains
<https://doi.org/10.36333/rs10>

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #1 – Managing forest disturbances in a changing climate

- **Disturbances often interact and magnify impacts:** bark beetles and wildfire often build on initial windthrow and drought disturbances
- **Disturbances offer opportunities for adaptation:** recovery after disturbances opens a window for increasing species diversity

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #1 – Managing forest disturbances in a changing climate

Selected recommendations

- Adopt proactive forest management approaches, e.g. establishing **advance regeneration** or **reducing stand density**
- Adapt regulations and infrastructure to support CC adaptation: e.g. more **time for forest recovery**; consider **changing species suitability** in habitat guidelines; improve **storage and transport infrastructure**

Recommendations

- 1. Adapt Forest Management to Disturbances**
 - Consider short-term costs vs. long-term benefits: proactive management is more expensive upfront but reduces future damage.
 - Actively exploit disturbed patches as opportunities for climate change adaptation in forest management, using canopy openings to transition to mixed, climate-resilient tree species.
 - Incorporate post-disturbance forest structures into management (rather than eradicating them) to achieve important goals of sustainable forest management (e.g. increasing deadwood stocks in forests).
 - Adopt proactive approaches in both high-risk stands and those expected to become vulnerable in the future. These approaches may include establishing advance regeneration, reducing stand density and shortening rotation periods to lower risks.
 - Implement effective browsing control plans, which can be a decisive factor in post-disturbance restoration.
 - Develop best practices in adaptive management with recommendations for different forest conditions and disseminate to forest owners in national languages, e.g. via forest extension services.
- 2. Adapt regulations and infrastructure to support climate change adaptation**
 - Support forest owners in realizing adaptation measures with a combination of policy instruments, such as financial support, competence building and increased flexibility of regulations.
 - Remove the salvage requirement that is still a legal imperative in many EU countries and allow longer time windows for forest recovery following disturbances. This will facilitate the establishment of more diverse resilient forests.
 - Enable adaptation to climate change in guidelines for nature restoration and in habitat regulations for Natura2000 areas.
 - Safeguard nursery capacities and improve seed availability with the desired seeds for restoration, enabling potential use of reproductive material from neighbouring regions with suitable climate.
 - Support the establishment of storage and transport infrastructure to increase resilience in the wood value chain.
- 3. Improve Data and Planning**
 - Forest restoration requires close monitoring and silvicultural interventions to ensure desired long-term development.
 - Mainstream newly available information on potential future disturbance risks into landscape level planning tools and process-based models to guide management decision making.
 - Use emerging remote sensing approaches to apply targeted disturbance management strategies.

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #2 – The role of biodiversity in making forests resilient

- **Mixed forests are key to resilience:** Forests with diverse tree species are better equipped to withstand and recover from extreme weather events
- **Biodiversity is an irreplaceable forest service:** Forest biodiversity is among the hardest ecosystem services to substitute, making its conservation vital for forest resilience and functionality

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #2 – The role of biodiversity in making forests resilient

Selected recommendations

- **Decision makers:** Promote management for structural diversity incl. natural regeneration, uneven-aged forest & deadwood retention
- **Forest owners & managers:** Diversify your measures by tailoring to local needs, manage browsing and foster natural regeneration

RECOMMENDATIONS

For Policymakers (regional to EU level)

- a. **Promote tree diversity:**
 - o Support forests with tree species mixture with different functional traits to improve recovery from disturbances and make them more adaptable to climate change. Promote mixed forest with slow-growing broadleaved species and not only fast-growing conifers and support more mixture in coniferous stands.
 - o Foster the management of deer population to reduce browsing impacts: Browsing can be a risk to tree diversity, because deer feed on specific species, e.g. oak.
- b. **Promote forest management for structural diversity:**
 - o Foster natural regeneration in an early state to support biodiversity.
 - o Advance uneven-aged forests to increase resilience and to speed up recovery from disturbances.
 - o Promote deadwood retention and other measures to increase the diversity of the forest structure, allowing multiple species to coexist by meeting their specific habitat requirements.
- c. **Provide financial and training support for forest managers:**
 - o Develop training programs for forest owners on how to manage forests in ways that benefit biodiversity and increase resilience.

For Forest Owners and Managers

- a. **Support ecosystem and economic resilience through diversity:**
 - o Diversify tree species to reduce the risk of large-scale losses during extreme weather events.
 - o Balance biodiversity and timber production by creating forests with a mix of tree types and structures that support different species.
- b. **Use disturbances to spark biodiversity growth:**
 - o Retain natural features: after storms or fires, leave some deadwood and fallen trees to support biodiversity and provide habitat for wildlife.
 - o Mimic disturbances (e.g. via prescribed burning) as a forest management method to increase forest resilience and biodiversity promotion
- c. **Diversify your measures:**
 - o Tailor your management to local needs: Use strategies that work for specific regions and conditions, ensuring both biodiversity and economic goals are met.
 - o Set small forest patches aside.
 - o Manage browsing efficiently.
 - o Foster natural regeneration in an early state to support biodiversity.

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #3 – Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

Key statements

Uwe Kies (InnovaWood)

- Short term: Increased salvage logging will lead to market surplus of **lower quality wood**.
- Long term: Climate-resilient forests will favour **more mixed forests** with a higher proportion of hardwoods.
- We observe an **unbalanced risk gap between forest owners and wood industries**. Forest owners shoulder the biggest burden of the risks and face the highest costs.

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #3 – Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

Selected recommendations

- **Raise awareness of the risk gap:** streamlining adaptation efforts, promoting partnerships, and encouraging information exchange across the value chain.
- **Explore alternative species and novel applications,** including hardwoods.
 - a. Diversification and resource efficiency strategies
 - b. Innovation towards higher value-added products
 - c. Promote the cascading principle and a circular bioeconomy

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RESONATE WP X Task X

PB #3 – Enhancing climate resilience of forest value chains

An industry perspective

Dietmar Hagauer (Papierholz Austria)

- Short-term responses vs. longer-term adaptation needs
- Improved logistics important for value chain resilience
- Research supports innovation in the industry
- Be aware of resilience trade-offs (e.g. set aside reduces resource availability)
- Mutual understanding of value chain dependencies is needed!

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RESONATE WP X Task X

Perspectives on forest (value chain) resilience

- RESONATE established improved scientific knowledge about forest resilience in different contexts
- Different resilience perspectives may not always align
- In our workshop we hope to broaden the RESONATE recommendations on enhancing forest resilience with your views, expectations, and needs

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7.4 Closing session presentation

RESONATE
Resilient Forests for Society

Workshop conclusions
Marcus Lindner

Rooting for Resilience - Policy Workshop
Brussels, 10 Feb 2025

EFI Innovawood pi Prospek Institute

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Thank you for the inspiring workshop!

What is next?

- We will produce a workshop report with key outcomes on Recommendations & Research Needs
- Two synthesizing RESONATE deliverables are in progress
 - A scientific synthesis report (D5.5)
 - A report with policy (and practice) recommendations (D5.6)
- Policy drop-in sessions on 6th of March 2025 (Forestry House, Brussels)
 - Presentation of the two final RESONATE reports
 - Time to ask questions about the science behind the RESONATE recommendations
- RESONATE is ending 31st March 2025

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Thank you!

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RESONATE project meeting 2023 – visit to CS Croatia

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- website www.resonateforest.org
- X account @RESONATE_forest
- EFI's 'Resilience Blog' <https://resilience-blog.com/>
- EFI's LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-forest-institute>

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- RESONATE: Resilient forest value chains – enhancing resilience through natural and socio-economic responses. Horizon 2020 RIA. Project no. 101000574, April 2021 – March 2025.
- Contact: Marcus.Lindner@efi.int

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